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D13.5 Dissemination and Communication activities report (final version)

(Version 3.0, 29/03/2024)

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Abbreviations

CTA	Call To Action
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current document under the title D13.5 “Dissemination and Communication activities report (final version)” provides an overview of the dissemination and communication strategy implemented by the VITALISE project during the period, from October 2022 to March 2024 (M19-M36). The aim of the strategy was to promote the project, engage stakeholders, and maximize impact.

The present deliverable addresses two aspects, each focusing on different elements of the dissemination and communication strategy. Particularly, the first aspect highlights the various communication tools and channels utilized, including the project website, social media accounts, newsletter, YouTube channel, press releases, call to action campaigns, and promotional materials. Insights and analytics for each channel are also presented. The second one focuses on the communication and dissemination activities conducted during the period, such as organizing events like the VITALISE Summer School, Innovate to Thrive webinar series, and Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. It also covers participation in third-party events, direct contact with stakeholders, collaboration with other projects, press coverage, and publications.

D13.5 is a public deliverable of this project, part of the WP13, and is the update and completion of the D13.2 “Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)”, developed according to the D13.1 “Dissemination and Communication plan” that was submitted to the European Commission in M3 (June 2021). Also, the D13.2 “Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)” was submitted in M18 (September 2022). Information concerning the project’s scope and objectives as well as WP13 is also presented to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the Description of Action (DoA), and the other WP13 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with, the DoA and the Grant Agreement (GA) but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

It needs to be noted that for the development and execution of the relevant Task, the WP Leader, as well as all the involved members, have advised and considered the following official EU document guidelines¹, in full line with the contractual agreement and corresponding articles.

¹ Commission, E., 2022. Communicating Your Project - H2020 Online Manual. [online] Ec.europa.eu. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm> [Accessed 1 March 2024]. and Commission, E., 2022. Dissemination & Exploitation - Open Access - H2020 Online Manual. [online] Ec.europa.eu. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm> [Accessed 1 March 2024].

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability

This work package is responsible for coordinating the dissemination and exploitation efforts of the project, as well as communicating the project's outcomes and activities with external parties. It actively plans, executes, and reports on relevant activities, ensuring that VITALISE actively participates in collaborative events and forms partnerships with other projects. It also facilitates collaboration with external organizations in Europe and standards bodies.

According to the DoA, WP13 is assigned to:

- Raise awareness among participants, target groups, and European society about the existence of VITALISE, its objectives, progress, and results.
- Ensure that the project's results reach various target groups and European society, encouraging a dialogue about Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- Keep stakeholders updated with news and improvements related to VITALISE.
- Plan and assess the potential for exploitation and added value of all exploitable outcomes from VITALISE during and after the project.
- Co-design and co-develop sustainable business models based on the main results of VITALISE that will ensure its sustainability beyond the project's end.

1.3 The Deliverable D13.5

1.3.1 Purpose and Scope

The current deliverable aims to present the progress and results of the VITALISE project's dissemination and communication strategy over the period of M19 to M36 (October 2022 to March 2024).

This report includes:

- Updates on the dissemination and communication strategy.
- Final progress report on the communication channels and activities, both online and offline.
- Insights into the communication and dissemination activities conducted during the period.

1.3.2 Intended readership

The following table defines the intended audience of the current deliverable:

Table 1 Intended audience of the deliverable

Intended audience	Reasons for interest in reading
VITALISE Consortium partners	To be informed on the communication and dissemination activities performed by the consortium during the reporting period M19-M36.
European Commission	To review and assess this deliverable as a required report based on DoA of VITALISE project.
Identified stakeholders	To be informed about the communication and dissemination activities performed within the reporting period and discover how they could be benefited and/or engaged.
Partners participating in similar projects	To be used as a guide and practical tool for dissemination managers of on-going and future similar projects, who will be willing to explore VITALISE strategy and capitalize on it.
Anyone interested	To share knowledge, information, and lessons learnt during the implementation of the VITALISE project.

1.3.3 Structure of the Deliverable

The current document is structured into four distinct sections and 2 appendices. Specifically:

- **Chapter 1:** Introduces the reader to the VITALISE project, provides information about D13.5, defines the scope of the document, and identifies the intended audience.
- **Chapter 2:** Presents tools and channels used, describes actions taken during M19-M36, and discusses the impact on the audience.
- **Chapter 3:** Lists the communication and dissemination activities that have been carried out, highlighting specific actions like the Innovate to Thrive webinar series, the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium, and more.
- **Chapter 4:** Summarizes key points and issues addressed in the document.

1.3.4 Methodology

The creation of this deliverable was based on the close collaboration among the consortium for reporting efficiently the performed activities in the period of interest.

To streamline the reporting process, the VITALISE Consortium used to implement an online tool for tracking and documenting their dissemination and communication activities throughout the project. As part of this update, a new template was created in a Word document, aligned with the reporting requirements in the participants portal. This new reporting method was designed to enhance clarity and readability, making it easier for partners to provide the necessary information and for ViLabs to receive, analyse, and utilize that information effectively.

Each partner communicated the progress and developments on the topic to ViLabs and on a biannual basis, they provided with a consolidated report summarizing their activities to ensure the quality of the information provided.

1.3.5 Quality of the document

For ensuring the quality of the current document, ViLabs as WP13 leader, prepared the initial draft and distributed to the intended project partners, ENoLL and AV, for review and contribution. Additionally, before the final submission to the EC, the document was sent again to the project coordinator for their final approval. It is important to note that the deliverable is written in English and follows the correct template specified by the project. Furthermore, a thorough language quality control check has been conducted to ensure accuracy and clarity.

1.3.6 Relation to other WP13 deliverables

This deliverable is interrelated with the other WP13 deliverables too. The table below explains the dependencies and relation of each one:

Table 2 List of WP13 deliverables

Title of WP13 Deliverable	Dependencies and relation with D6.4
D13.1 "Dissemination and Communication plan" (M3)	<p>Presents the plan of the dissemination and communication strategy that VITALISE employs to achieve promotion and impact of the project outcomes to the targeted audiences.</p> <p>D13.5 reports the actions made following the plan as described in D13.1.</p>
D13.2 "Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)" (M18)	<p>Details all the dissemination, communication and outreach activities that have been implemented within the VITALISE Project from M1 until M18.</p> <p>D13.5 reports the activities that implemented during the period M19-M36.</p>

2 Communication Tools and Channels

Section 2 of the current document presents a comprehensive overview of the communication tools utilized by the consortium between M19-M36. Additionally, it highlights the various actions undertaken using these tools during the same time frame. Together with chapter 3, this section forms the main body of the document.

2.1 VITALISE website

The most important online communication channel, for all kinds of project, is the website. It plays a key role in transmitting the desired messages to target groups and ensures its presence in all available online search engines. [VITALISE website](#) serves as the major mean of information for communicating with the stakeholders and disseminating its results to a wide audience.

2.1.1 Website Content

The website represents a major channel of information and communication for visitors and, for this reason, is harmonized and interrelated with the main goals of WP13 to disseminate the project findings as well as to engage key stakeholders with a view to knowledge sharing.

The website serves as a central hub for the project's identity, goals, and actions, providing stakeholders with comprehensive information. Essentially, the VITALISE website functions as a powerful tool for disseminating and communicating the project's research results and outcomes. In this respect, the project's communication managers have been diligently working to optimize the user's experience and provide various means of connectivity. All communication and dissemination tools, channels, repositories, materials, documents, and social media platforms are seamlessly linked to the project website, ensuring easy access and engagement for stakeholders.

2.1.2 Updated Site Map

During the second reporting period of the VITALISE project, the website underwent updates to enhance its functionality and provide a more **result-oriented** experience for its users. As part of these updates, a new category called "outputs" was introduced within the website's sections.

The "outputs" section serves as a comprehensive repository of the project's public deliverables, scientific publications, and materials. It also showcases the results obtained from several actions conducted within the context of the VITALISE project. By adding the "outputs" category, the Communication manager aims to provide easy access to important project-related information and findings.

Figure 1 VITALISE Website Updated Sitemap

Overall, the inclusion of the “outputs” category on the VITALISE website enables users to conveniently access and retrieve relevant documents, research papers, and other materials that contribute to the overall progress and accomplishments of the project. This addition enhances the user experience by providing a more efficient way to explore and access valuable resources related to the VITALISE project.

2.1.3 Blog Posts and News Items

The website serves as a platform to share all relevant information about the project with various audiences. It is regularly updated to ensure continued interest in the project's activities. The updates focus on project news, events, relevant blogposts, press releases, newsletters, collaborations, and other dissemination efforts.

For attracting more traffic at the website and generally gain more visibility for the project, non-scientific articles (original content) were written by the consortium partners and uploaded at the VITALISE “Press” section. More specifically, they can be found at “[News](#)” section. More information is available in the table below:

Table 3 List of News-items at VITALISE website

No.	Partner/s	Month	Article	URL
1	VILABS	October 2022	VITALISE Info day 2nd Open Call	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-info-day-2nd-open-call/
2	VILABS	October 2022	VITALISE INFO DAY 2nd Open Call Online event	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-info-day-2nd-open-call-online-event/
3	VILABS, AUTH	November 2022	VITALISE celebrated Open Access Week 2022	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-celebrated-open-access-week-2022/
4	VILABS	December 2022	Third Meeting of the VITALISE Harmonisation Body	https://vitalise-project.eu/third-meeting-of-the-vitalise-harmonisation-body/
5	VILABS	January 2023	The 2nd Open Call of VITALISE just ended, but a new chapter begins!	https://vitalise-project.eu/the-2nd-open-call-of-vitalise-just-ended-but-a-new-chapter-begins/
6	VILABS	March 2023	VITALISE 3rd Open Call Launched Apply NOW!	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-3rd-open-call-launched-apply-now/
7	VILABS	March 2023	VITALISE Call for External Evaluators	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-call-for-external-evaluators/
8	VILABS	March 2023	VITALISE INFO Day 3rd Open Call	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-info-day-3rd-open-call/
9	VILABS	March 2023	Deadline Extended VITALISE Call for External Evaluators	https://vitalise-project.eu/deadline-extended-vitalise-call-for-external-evaluator/

10	VILABS	March 2023	VITALISE Summer School 2023 on Living Labs & Commercialization Bootcamp	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2023-on-living-labs/
11	VILABS	April 2023	VITALISE Plenary Meeting Vienna, Austria	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-plenary-meeting-vienna-austria/
12	VILABS, AUTH	April 2023	VITALISE presented at INTEGER Project Meeting Krakow, Poland	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-presented-at-integer-project-meeting-krakow-poland/
13	VILABS	May 2023	Deadline Extended VITALISE 3rd Open Call	https://vitalise-project.eu/deadline-extended-vitalise-3rd-open-call/
14	VILABS	May 2023	APPLY NOW!! VITALISE Summer School 2023 on Living Labs & Commercialization Bootcamp	https://vitalise-project.eu/apply-now-vitalise-summer-school-2023-on-living-labs-commercialization-bootcamp/
15	VILABS, AUTH	May 2023	VITALISE supports the Museum Day!	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-supports-the-museum-day/
16	VILABS, AUTH	May 2023	Applied working session: “The role of scientific research and research expertise in Horizon Europe projects” VITALISE presentations.	https://vitalise-project.eu/applied-working-session-the-role-of-scientific-research-and-research-expertise-in-horizon-europe-projects-vitalise-presentations/
17	VILABS, AUTH	May 2023	VITALISE visit to Jagiellonian University	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-visit-to-jagiellonian-university/
18	VILABS	June 2023	VITALISE Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp An Event of Resounding Success	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2023-completed/
19	VILABS	June 2023	Deadline Extended VITALISE 3rd Open Call	https://vitalise-project.eu/3rd_cut_off_extended/

20	VILABS	June 2023	VITALISE Public Deliverables available now on ZENODO	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-public-deliverables-now-available-on-zenodo/
21	VILABS, McGill	June 2023	VITALISE project: A real life success story of Canada Partnering with Horizon Europe Mc Gill Presentation at ECCIR webinar	https://vitalise-project.eu/canada-horizon-europe/
22	VILABS	June 2023	VITALISE Launches SlideShare Account	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-launches-slideshare-channel/
23	VILABS	June 2023	VITALISE NEWS 4th VITALISE Newsletter Issue published!	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-news-4th-vitalise-newsletter-issue-published/
24	VILABS	July 2023	VITALISE News Open Living Lab Days 2023	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-news-open-living-lab-days-2023/
25	VILABS	July 2023	VITALISE welcomes GILL project to its network!	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-gill-synergy/
26	VILABS	September 2023	5th Meeting of the Harmonization Body Join Us!	https://vitalise-project.eu/5th-meeting-of-the-harmonization-body-join-us/
27	VILABS	September 2023	Unlock the Full Potential of Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation with VITALISE	https://vitalise-project.eu/unlock-the-full-potential-of-living-labs-and-collaborative-innovation-with-vitalise/
28	VILABS, LAUREA	October 2023	VITALISE News Living Lab Expert Dr. Teemu Santonen Honored with Veli Pekka Niitamo Award for Best Research Paper	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-news-living-lab-expert-dr-teemu-santonen-honored-with-veli-pekka-niitamo-award-for-best-research-paper/
29	VILABS	October 2023	VITALISE Participation in Open Living Lab Days 2023	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-participation-in-open-living-lab-days-2023/
30	VILABS	October 2023	VITALISE Unveils Virtual Access Service for Open	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-unveils-virtual-access-service-

			Research Advancements	for-open-research-advancements/
31	VILABS	October 2023	VITALISE Joins the EU INTEGER Collaboratory at Open Living Lab Days	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-joins-the-eu-integer-collaboratory-at-open-living-lab-days/
32	VILABS, TREBAG	October 2023	VITALISE News TREBAG Awarded as Best Oral Presentation at European Sport Congress	https://vitalise-project.eu/best-oral-presentation-european-sport-congress/
33	VILABS	October 2023	5+1 Reasons Why to Apply for Virtual Access	https://vitalise-project.eu/51-reasons-why-to-apply-for-virtual-access/
34	VILABS	November 2023	VITALISE Unveils Accelup Platform to Drive Innovation Thessaloniki Meeting	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-unveils-accelup-platform-to-drive-innovation-thessaloniki-meeting/
35	VILABS	December 2023	VITALISE Plenary Meeting in Madrid, Spain	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-plenary-meeting-in-madrid-spain/
36	VILABS	December 2023	Official Launch Announcement: VITALISE's Virtual Access to Datasets is Now Live!	https://vitalise-project.eu/virtual-access-launch/
37	VILABS	December 2023	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium Save the Date!	https://vitalise-project.eu/health-and-wellbeing-living-lab-symposium-save-the-date/
38	VILABS, AV	January 2024	Pitch Clinic Event Save-The-Dates	https://vitalise-project.eu/pitch-clinic-event-save-the-dates/
39	VILABS	February 2024	VITALISE Recognized as Best Practice in SSH Integration within Horizon 2020	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-recognized-as-best-practice-in-ssh-integration-within-horizon-2020/

Additionally, a new section has been created dedicated to showcasing **Transnational Access Program** stories. These stories are presented in the form of blog posts, highlighting the enriching experiences of researchers who have participated in the Transnational Access program within the research infrastructure as part of the VITALISE project. Therefore, every partner has contributed a blog post outlining their specific contributions and insights. These blogposts have been uploaded to

VITALISE outputs section and can be found in “[Transnational Access Blogs](#)” section. More information is available in the table below:

Table 4 List of Transnational Access Blogs at VITALISE website

No.	Partner/s	Month	Blogpost	URL
1	TREBAG	October 2023	A Joint Transnational Access Program of Cyprus, Belgium and Hungary on the use of VR glasses in the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab in Hungary	https://vitalise-project.eu/transnational-access-program-cyprus-belgium-hungary/
2	LAUREA	October 2023	A Researcher’s Journey at Laurea Living Labs	https://vitalise-project.eu/a-researchers-journey-at-laurea-living-labs/
3	TREBAG	October 2023	A Research Visit and Joint Research between the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab in Hungary and the University of Malaga	https://vitalise-project.eu/a-research-visit-and-joint-research-between-the-nagykovacsi-wellbeing-living-lab-in-hungary-and-the-university-of-malaga/
4	AUTH	November 2023	“Gold Health Care” project: Collaborating for Better Healthcare	https://vitalise-project.eu/gold-health-care-project-collaborating-for-better-healthcare/
5	AUTH	January 2024	Exploring IoT Horizons: A Journey into Privacy and Data Protection Mental Health Challenges	https://vitalise-project.eu/exploring-iot-horizons-a-journey-into-privacy-and-data-protection-mental-health-challenges/
6	AUTH	January 2024	Navigating Multitasking Realities in the Academic Digital Landscape	https://vitalise-project.eu/navigating-multitasking-realities-in-the-academic-digital-landscape/
7	LICALAB	January 2024	ChatterGlove – an exoskeleton for hearing impaired individuals	https://vitalise-project.eu/chatterglove-an-exoskeleton-for-hearing-impaired-individuals/
8	AUTH	January 2024	Unveiling Pioneering “ASSURE”: Dysphagia	https://vitalise-project.eu/unveiling-assure-pioneering-

			Screening with Cutting-Edge Technology	dysphagia-screening-with-cutting-edge-technology/
9	LICALAB	January 2024	Physical Activity and Physical Function in Mid-Life Women	https://vitalise-project.eu/physical-activity-and-physical-function-in-mid-life-women/
10	LICALAB	January 2024	Using digital health and wellbeing technologies: bother or burden?	https://vitalise-project.eu/using-digital-health-and-wellbeing-technologies-bother-or-burden/
11	LICALAB	January 2024	Sound Wellbeing in Later Life: Exploring wellbeing through contextual understanding of sound and sonic reminiscence	https://vitalise-project.eu/sound-wellbeing-in-later-life-exploring-wellbeing-through-contextual-understanding-of-sound-and-sonic-reminiscence/
12	AIT	February 2024	Evaluation Pilot of a Socially Assistive Robot and Brain-Computer Interface for Upper Limb Rehabilitation	https://vitalise-project.eu/evaluation-pilot-of-a-socially-assistive-robot-and-brain-computer-interface-for-upper-limb-rehabilitation/

2.1.4 Website Analytics

The communication managers were constantly auditing the website's performance to have a clear picture of its outreach. Google Analytics allows the mapping of the traffic and tracking of the number of visitors and other relevant metrics over the last year of the project.

Data retrieved on 20th March 2024 from Google Analytics on the VITALISE website.

Starting with the website performance, based on the Google Analytics tool, the first category is **User Acquisition**, to obtain an overview of our users' behaviour.

Figure 2 User acquisition (M19-M36)

According to figure 2, one can observe the following numbers:

Table 5 User acquisition (M19-M36)

Field	Data
New users	11,501
Engaged sessions	11,284
Engagement rate	51.08%
Engaged sessions per user	0.94
Average engagement time	1m 24s
Event count	134,824

The communication manager during the project’s lifecycle assessed these numbers regularly and tracked the website’s shortcomings to find the most efficient way for its optimisation.

An explanation of terms is available below:

- New users: The number of users who interacted with your site or launched your app for the first time (event-triggered: first open);
- Engaged sessions: The number of sessions that lasted longer than 10 seconds, had a conversion event or had two or more screen or page views.
- Engagement rate: The percentage of engaged sessions. (Engaged sessions divided by sessions).
- Engaged sessions per user: Engaged sessions divided per user

- Average engagement time: The average length of time that the app was in the foreground or the website had a focus in the browser.
- Event count: The number of times your users triggered an event.

Another important piece of information about the website, refer to the **most popular pages**. By tracking them, the communication manager can understand what the visitors are more interested in and can organise a more efficient communication plan for each page.

Figure 3 Popular pages (M19-M36)

According to the figure above, during months 19 to 36, one can observe the following numbers:

Table 6 Pages and Screens (M19-M36)

Field	Data
Views	40,572
Users	12,052
Views per user	3.37

Additional definitions are presented below:

- Views: The number of app screens or web pages your users saw. Repeated views of a single screen or page are counted. (screen_view + page_view events);
- Users: The total number of active users;
- Views per user: Views divided per users.

The most popular page is the home page (9,554 views), followed by the pages “Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures” (4,982 views), “Health and Living Lab Symposium” (1,614 views), “Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation” (1,449 views), and “Living Labs” (1,242 views).

Examining the peaks in website views depicted in Figure 3, it's evident that certain events and the corresponding promotion actions drove significant traffic to relevant sections of the website. For instance, on October 10th, 2022, there was a notable increase in views in the “Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures” section, coinciding with the promotion of the 2nd call through project’s social media channels. Similarly, in the period from September to October 2023, there was a surge in visits to the “Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation” section, due to the promotional activities that took place this period, such as social media posts and call to action campaigns.

Additionally, peaks observed on January 23rd, 2024, and February 20th, 2024, were attributed to the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. This event drove significant traffic to the corresponding sections of the website. Like the rest of the events conducted during the project’s lifecycle, relevant social media posts, call to actions campaigns and newsletters were facilitated to promote the event and increase its visibility.

In summary, the coordinated efforts of posting relevant content on social media, the call-to-action campaigns, and the newsletters, along with directing users to specific website pages, have significantly enhanced the visibility and engagement of the VITALISE page. This integrated approach has effectively leveraged social media platforms to drive traffic and engagement on the VITALISE website.

2.2 Social Media

Social media channels enable the dissemination and communication activities, enhancing the project's outreach. This section aims to present some representative elements of the impact of VITALISE social media and the results of this reporting period (M19-M36) per social media channels. The feature provided by the social media platforms has played an important role for the organisations and the communications of the project’s events, also working as the key info point and a point of reference even at the project’s website. The links of the VITALISE social media channels are the following:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/VITALISEproject>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vitalise-project/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCTvXvqIRLL29-3d9LTulq3A>

The project’s social media accounts were updated with posts of:

- VITALISE publications;
- VITALISE events organized by the consortium;
- VITALISE e-newsletter issues;
- Non-scientific articles written by the VITALISE consortium and published at the project’s website;
- VITALISE profiles on digital publishing platforms (i.e. SlideShare);
- Other project news (participation in public events, presence in press and media etc.);
- News and events related to the project’s topic.

More audience was attracted, and visibility was increased by adding the following hashtags in the aforementioned types of posts:

- #HealthAndWellbeing
- #LivingLab
- #ResearchInfrastructure
- #Harmonisation
- #DataAnalysis
- #OpenScience
- #EU_Project

- #H2020
- Other words relevant with project's publications
- Official hashtags of public events where consortium partners presented the project

2.2.1 VITALISE Facebook Page

Facebook is a popular social networking platform that allows users to connect with friends, family, and businesses online. A Facebook page is a dedicated profile for businesses, organizations, public figures, and other entities to share information, engage with their audience, and promote their products or services. It provides businesses with a platform to create a presence on Facebook and interact with their customers. Meta Business Suite, previously known as Facebook Business Suite, is a tool provided by Facebook for businesses to manage their presence and activity across Facebook, Instagram, and Messenger. It offers features such as scheduling posts, analyzing performance metrics, and responding to messages from customers.²

[VITALISE Facebook page](#) currently counts 246 followers. This platform served as a primary channel for disseminating project-related updates, showcasing progress, sharing valuable tools and project materials, and promoting events organized by either the project itself or its collaborative partners.

Figure 4 VITALISE Facebook page

Based on the data collected on March 20, 2024, the VITALISE Facebook account has experienced a 49.1% increase in user reach compared to the previous reporting period, reaching a total of 11.8K users.

Among the posts, the [Accelup Meeting](#) garnered the highest reach, reaching 1.3K users. Following closely was the post about the [first day of the VITALISE Commercialization Bootcamp](#) that reached 1.2K users.

² Source: <https://www.facebook.com/business/help/966883707418907> (Facebook Help)

Figure 5 Reach - Facebook page

The VITALISE page has also seen a significant increase in visits, with 1.9K visits during this period, which represents a 283.6% increase (Figure 6). Notably, January and March 2024 witnessed significant spikes in visits, coinciding with a series of posts promoting various VITALISE initiatives and events.

In January and March 2024, the page was consistently active, showcasing events such as the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium, the Pitch Clinic Event, and the Virtual Access initiative. These posts effectively drew attention to VITALISE's ongoing efforts and garnered increased engagement from the audience.

Moreover, in the start of June 2023, the page experienced heightened visibility due to daily updates on the Summer School on Living Labs 2023 and Commercialization Bootcamp. This consistent stream of content kept the audience engaged and contributed to the project's Facebook page visibility.

Finally, the posts regarding the Museum Day, the project's Plenary meeting in Austria, the 2nd Open call and more, also seems to increase the VITALISE's page visits during the second reporting period.

Figure 6 Visits - Facebook page

Furthermore, the published content on the VITALISE Facebook page has generated over 2K reactions, indicating a 77.6% increase, and has received more than 156 link clicks for additional content or information. Among the posts, those discussing the outcomes of the Open Living Lab Days garnered the highest interaction rates. This underscores the audience's interest in this event and its outcomes.

Figure 7 Content Interactions - Facebook page

2.2.2 VITALISE X Account (ex-Twitter)

Twitter is a popular social media platform that allows users to share and discover information through short messages called "tweets." Users can follow other accounts to see their tweets on their timeline and engage with them through likes, retweets, and replies. Twitter is known for its character limit of 280 characters per tweet, which encourages concise and succinct communication. It has become a

powerful tool for individuals, businesses, and organizations to connect with a global audience and share their thoughts, opinions, and news in real-time.³

The [VITALISE account on X](#), which currently has 302 followers, was mainly used to promote participatory activities, awareness-raising events, exploitation activities and the project progress in general. It is a great tool to connect with most of the relevant stakeholders.

Figure 8 VITALISE X Profile

Since Twitter divides the reporting periods into trimesters, the table below adds up the periods separately. The overall numbers for M19-M36 are presented in Table 7 below, which shows overall data from Twitter Analytics for the VITALISE page within the reporting period.

Table 7 Twitter performance (M19-M36)

Field	Data
Impressions	10.2 K
Engagement rate	5.42 %

The performance during March and May 2023 stands out, boasting a combined total of 3.1K impressions and an average engagement rate of 6.3% per post (figure 8). These months were marked by several VITALISE events promotion, such as the Summer School 2023, the 3rd Open Call and the VITALISE Info Days. This positive trend in VITALISE online presence and engagement highlights the impact of the communication activities during this specific period.

³ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twitter> (Wikipedia)

One of the standout posts during this timeframe was the [announcement of registration for the Summer School on Living Labs 2023 and Commercialization Bootcamp](#), published on May 9th, 2023. This post garnered an impressive 534 views, indicating a high level of interest and engagement from the audience. Similarly, another [post promoting the same event](#), shared on May 5th, 2023, reached 251 views. These analytics underscore the effectiveness of consistent promotion and the audience's strong interest in this event.

Figure 9 March-May 2023 performance

2.2.3 VITALISE LinkedIn Page

LinkedIn is a professional networking platform that connects individuals from various industries and sectors. It serves as a virtual resume, allowing users to showcase their skills, experiences, and professional achievements. LinkedIn enables professionals to expand their networks, connect with potential employers or clients, and stay updated on industry trends and insights. With its emphasis on professional development and career growth, LinkedIn has become an essential tool for both job seekers and businesses looking to establish their presence in the professional world.⁴

⁴ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LinkedIn> (Wikipedia)

Figure 10 VITALISE LinkedIn Profile

The VITALISE LinkedIn page currently counts 874 followers from different industries, like Research (26.3%), Program and Project Management (8.4%), Business Development (7.6%), Engineering (7.2%) and such. Also, VITALISE followers come from different places around Europe, such as Greece, Ireland, Spain, Slovenia, Italy, Austria and more. It is encouraging to see that the project has gained followers from many different industries and locations, which means that people from different backgrounds are interested in learning more about the challenge of convenient and open access to research infrastructures.

Figure 11 LinkedIn Analytics – Followers main industries and locations

Since the LinkedIn allows users to access and review data up to a maximum of one year in the past, the information presented below concerns the period from March 2023 to March 2024. Specifically, this period of time, the page gained more than 24,407 impressions during this reporting period, with June and October, 2023 and February 2024 being the months with the best performance (figure 12).

In June 2023, the VITALISE Summer School and Commercialization Bootcamp were took place and final call announcements as well as updates from each day of the event shared through VITALISE’s LinkedIn account. This resulted in heightened audience engagement, reflecting a substantial level

of interest in this milestone. Similarly, October 2023 were highlighted mainly by the VITALISE Webinar Series as well as the Open Living Lab Days 2023 recap, the introduction of Virtual Access and more. Finally, February 2024, was the month where the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium and the VITALISE Pitch Clinic Event took place. For this reason the corresponding posts for promoting these events were published during the month, increasing the account's engagement.

The **most engaging post** during this reporting period was published on October 9th, 2023, and was [a recap of VITALISE Open Living Lab Days 2023](#). This post gathered 1,579 impressions and 221 link clicks. The posts that followed, in terms of engagement, was the [report of the final day of Summer School](#) with 919 impressions and 191 link clicks as well as the [report of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium](#), which gathered 949 impressions and 368 link clicks. The above numbers, indicate the strong interest of the audience in these events and their outcomes that were organized by the VITALISE Consortium.

Figure 12 Post impressions

2.3 YouTube

YouTube is a popular online platform that allows users to share, watch, and interact with a vast array of videos. It has revolutionized the way we consume and create content, offering a wide range of videos, including educational tutorials, entertainment, music, news, and much more. YouTube provides a space for individuals, content creators, and businesses to reach a global audience, build communities, and express their creativity. With its user-friendly interface and powerful search algorithms, YouTube has become a go-to source for information, entertainment, and inspiration for millions of people worldwide.

2.3.1 VITALISE YouTube Channel

The [VITALISE channel on YouTube](#), currently counts 53 subscribers and 9 videos has been uploaded. It hosts a series of informative videos related to the project. These videos aim to provide insights on the different aspects of the VITALISE project, including the Info days conducted, the Harmonization Body meetings as well as project meetings. These videos serve as valuable resources for individuals interested in learning more about the project's objectives and activities.

Figure 13 VITALISE YouTube channel

2.4 Newsletter

The newsletter is a dissemination tool that assisted WP13 in reaching the target audiences and conveying to them the major VITALISE developments and results with main aim to attract their attention and engage them.

The VITALISE project, during its lifecycle, maintained a regular newsletter schedule, depending on project updates and needs. Currently, the VITALISE newsletter reaches a dedicated audience of 156 subscribers. During the reporting period 4 newsletter issues was published, in M19, M27, M35 and M36 that followed the activity of the project and the produced results. These newsletters were opened 676 times by the subscribers and generated 102 clicks, showing that the content was of interest to the audience and encouraged them to explore further.

For distributing (via email) the e-newsletter issues the free service of Mailchimp were used. Mailchimp is a powerful email marketing platform that enables businesses and individuals to create, send, and analyze email campaigns. With user-friendly features and a variety of customizable templates, Mailchimp makes it easy to design professional and engaging emails. Additionally, it provides advanced analytics to track the effectiveness of campaigns, allowing users to make data-driven decisions and optimize their email marketing strategies.

During the lifespan of the VITALISE project, interested individuals had the option to voluntarily subscribe to the newsletter through the contact section on the VITALISE website. By providing their email, name, and surname, subscribers were able to stay informed about the project's latest developments, outcomes, and activities. This subscription allowed them to receive regular updates directly in their inbox, ensuring they never missed important information.

It's important to note that subscribers always had the option to unsubscribe (opt-out) from the newsletter at any time. This ensured that the subscription was in compliance with GDPR policies, respecting the privacy and preferences of the subscribers.

2.4.1 Newsletter Issue No.3

The [3rd VITALISE newsletter](#) published on October 2022 and focuses on key topics such as the second open call for Transnational Access. At the same time, it highlights the participation of VITALISE partners in the Open Living Lab Days event. The newsletter introduces Accelup, an online platform aimed at revolutionizing how Living Labs offer services and network, creating equal opportunities for sustainable innovation partnerships. Additionally, the newsletter shares inspiring success stories from project partners, showcasing their motivations and visions.

Figure 14 VITALISE Newsletter - 3rd issue

2.4.2 Newsletter Issue No.4

The [4th VITALISE newsletter](#) published in June 2023 and focuses in the VITALISE Summer School 2023 on Living Labs and Commercialization Bootcamp. The newsletter also highlights the project's dissemination activities, research infrastructure visits, and important meetups with the VITALISE community.

Figure 15 VITALISE Newsletter - 4th issue

2.4.3 Newsletter Issue No. 5

The [5th VITALISE newsletter](#), distributed in February 2024, prominently highlighted two upcoming events: the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium and the VITALISE Pitch Clinic Event. Additionally, the newsletter served as a platform for disseminating important updates, including insights from the Innovate to Thrive webinars, blog posts with stories from the Transnational Access Activities and many more.

D13.5 Dissemination and Communication activities report (final version)

Figure 16 VITALISE Newsletter - 5th issue

2.4.4 Newsletter Issue No. 6

The 6th VITALISE Newsletter, published in March 2024. This issue was dedicated to the project's final event, the "Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium", that took place on February 20th in Brussels, Belgium and marked the end of the VITALISE project highlighting its significant impact on the research community and the Living Lab community.

Figure 17 VITALISE Newsletter - 6th issue

2.5 Press Releases

Press releases are powerful tools used to effectively communicate the outcomes and events of the project to various stakeholders. Serving as a concise and informative introduction, press releases provide a platform for sharing key information with the media and the public. By highlighting project achievements, milestones, and upcoming events, press releases ensure that the project's message reaches a wider audience, generating awareness and interest. With their ability to capture attention and deliver key messages, press releases play an essential role in disseminating important project updates and fostering meaningful engagement between the project and its stakeholders.

2.5.1 1st Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

During the reporting period, the project partners published one press release focused on the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. This press release played a vital role in disseminating important updates and generating interest in the symposium among stakeholders and the public.

Figure 18 Symposium Press Release

The press release for the 1st Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels highlighted the project's successful demonstration of how Living Labs can advance healthcare research. By bringing together experts and stakeholders, the symposium emphasized the importance of Living Labs as Research Infrastructures for future innovation in healthcare and wellbeing. The event sparked valuable discussions and collaborations, paving the way for further progress in utilizing Living Labs to improve healthcare outcomes.

2.6 Call to Action Campaigns

During this reporting period, Mailchimp was utilized by the Dissemination manager to promote and inform subscribed users about upcoming events. These campaigns served as a pivotal communication tool, facilitating the dissemination of vital information regarding forthcoming events to our subscribers and ensuring effective engagement and participation from our audience.

2.6.1 VITALISE 2nd OPEN CALL

On the 21st of October 2022, a [Call to Action campaign](#) was sent to promote the **second VITALISE Open Call**. The information provided through this campaign was regarding the Transnational Access opportunities while it highlights the benefits of participating in the open call and encourages researchers to apply before the deadline.

Figure 19 CTA - 2nd Open Call

2.6.2 3rd VITALISE Harmonization Body meeting

A [Call to Action campaign](#) was sent to subscribers on the 22nd of December, 2022, regarding the **3rd Harmonization Body Meeting** scheduled for **January 17th, 2023**. The campaign comprehensively detailed the meeting particulars, including the date, time, and place. Additionally, subscribers were informed about the agenda and the registration process.

Figure 20 First CTA - 3rd Harmonization Body meeting

2.6.3 3rd Harmonization Body Meeting is tomorrow! Register NOW!

In addition to the first [Call to Action campaign](#) addressing the **3rd Harmonization Body Meeting**, a second campaign was issued to subscribers on January 16, 2023, one day prior the meeting, to guarantee prompt reminders and maximum participation. The purpose of this follow-up email was to reinforce key details, such as the meeting's date, time, and place.

Figure 21 Second CTA - 3rd Harmonization body meeting

2.6.4 VITALISE Summer School 2023 on Living Labs & Commercialization Bootcamp | Register NOW!

A [Call to Action campaign](#) was deployed on the 18th of May 2023 to inform subscribers about the upcoming **Summer School 2023 on Living Labs and the Commercialization Bootcamp** scheduled for June 6th to 9th, 2023. The primary objective of this campaign was to provide subscribers with essential details pertaining to the event, including dates, location, registration deadline, program highlights, and other pertinent information. By disseminating comprehensive event details, we aimed to encourage subscriber engagement and participation.

Figure 22 CTA - Summer School 2023

2.6.5 5th VITALISE Harmonization Body Meeting | Join Us!

On the 4th of September 2023, a [Call to Action campaign](#) about the **5th Harmonization Body Meeting** on the 15th of September, 2023, was sent to the subscribed users to promote the upcoming meeting and provide useful information to the interested parties.

Figure 23 First CTA - 5th Harmonization body meeting

2.6.6 5th VITALISE Harmonization Body Meeting | Register Now

In addition to the initial [Call to Action campaign](#) regarding the **5th Harmonization Body Meeting**, a second campaign was dispatched to subscribers on September 15th, 2023, two days before the meeting, to ensure timely reminders and maximum attendance. This follow-up communication aimed to reinforce key details while also provided the meeting’s agenda.

Figure 24 Second CTA - 5th Harmonization body meeting

2.6.7 Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation VITALISE Webinar Series

Another [Call to Action campaign](#) was distributed to promote the **Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation webinars** scheduled from October 11th to 13th, 2023. The campaign aimed to promote this initiative by emphasizing the importance of participation while providing details about the webinars that will be conducted.

Figure 25 CTA - Innovate to Thrive webinars

2.6.8 Virtual Access CTA

On the 21st of December 2023, a [Call to Action campaign](#) was sent to the subscribed users to announce the launch of **VITALISE's Virtual Access to Datasets**. The campaign defined the concept of virtual access, including how it works and how to apply.

Figure 26 CTA - Virtual Access Launch

2.6.9 Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

To enhance the visibility and engagement of the **Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium**, a [Call to Action campaign](#) was created and disseminated via the Mailchimp platform to the subscribed users. The campaign not only outlined the upcoming Symposium but also informed about the Open Call for contributors.

The screenshot shows an email layout for the 'Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium'. At the top is the VITALISE logo and the text 'Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure'. Below this is a banner for the symposium, dated 13 February 2024 in Brussels, Belgium. A 'Register Now' button is prominently displayed. The main text describes the symposium's goal: to engage in collective reflection with the European Commission and stakeholders. A list of partner logos is shown below, including LAU, LICeap, Intras, TREBAG, GAIA, vChes, and others. The footer contains funding information from the European Union's Horizon 2020 program and a copyright notice for VITALISE Project.

Figure 27 CTA - Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

2.6.10 Updated Symposium Invitation

Additionally, a second [Call to Action campaign](#) was dispatched to the subscribed audience, informing about the upcoming **Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium**. This campaign aimed to raise awareness about the event and encourage even more registration, while also provided additional details about the event.

Over the past three years, a collaborative effort among Living Labs in Health has actively demonstrated the significance of Living Labs as Research Infrastructures, effectively representing the global Living Lab community. The work undertaken in VITALISE aligns with the overarching vision of Living Labs developed over the last 15 years, manifesting in project results that advance the recognition and quality of harmonized Living Labs.

The symposium's primary objective is to engage in collective reflection with the European Commission and relevant stakeholders and beneficiaries of Research Infrastructures. The aim is to discuss and plan the next steps toward a new era where Research Infrastructures are open and actively involve communities as powerful tools for co-research.

A second objective is to showcase completed or on-going research conducted within one or more Living Labs. This can be done through an oral presentation or a panel discussion/roundtable to the Symposium.

Join us for a unique opportunity for research presentation/discussion! Share your research and experience conducting research with the wider Living Lab community. Network and interact with fellow practitioners and researchers!

Open Call

social media logos: social media, LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc.

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You are receiving this email because you opted in via our website.

Figure 28 CTA - Updated Symposium Invitation

2.7 Promotional Materials

Promotional materials such as brochures, flyers, posters, and factsheets serve as essential dissemination and promotional tools for the project. They play a crucial role in establishing the project's identity, raising awareness, and increasing its visibility. These materials are designed to attract and motivate stakeholders to engage with the project, and they are often distributed during events, workshops, and conferences.

The content of these promotional materials is prepared by the leader of WP13 and then circulated to the consortium for review. Specific content is created for various project actions and events, aligning with relevant news items on the project's website and corresponding social media posts.

In the following sections, the promotional materials created during this reporting period are presented and organized based on their association with the specific situations.

2.7.1 Open Calls materials

To enhance the promotion of the **VITALISE Open Calls**, the Communication Manager has diligently prepared materials to effectively engage and inform stakeholders. These materials were thoughtfully designed to accompany various promotional activities such as social media posts, call to action campaigns, newsletters, and website news-items.

Specifically, the following materials have been created:

- **Factsheets:** Two-page factsheets have been developed for different TA researchers' categories, including entrepreneurs, LL practitioners, master's students, and academia. These factsheets aim to provide valuable information about the open call and its benefits.
- **Flyers:** Engaging and visually appealing flyers have been designed to attract attention and raise awareness about the VITALISE Open Calls. These flyers distill key information and encourage individuals to participate.
- **Banners (digital):** Eye-catching banners have been created to capture the attention of the target audience and promote the VITALISE Open Calls. These banners will be strategically placed in relevant locations to maximize visibility.

By employing these promotional materials, VITALISE aims to effectively communicate the value of the Open Calls and encourage active engagement from stakeholders. The above-mentioned materials are presented in the following figures:

Figure 29 2nd Open Call – Factsheets

Figure 30 2nd Open Call - Poster

Figure 31 3rd Open Call - Poster

2.7.2 VITALISE Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp

The **VITALISE Summer School 2023** was a collaborative effort between VITALISE's partners, aimed at delivering a comprehensive and impactful learning experience. The strategy that followed for raising the visibility of the event, attract potential participants, assist in raising the number of registrants along with promoting the results of the activity included several channels and tools deployed and used.

For the **promotion of the event**, the following promotional materials were created:

- **Poster:** The poster can be either printed and placed at the Venue of the event, or it can be placed in spaces where stakeholders can be informed about the event (before its realization). It includes a QR code where anyone interested in can scan the code and redirected to the VITALISE website at the dedicated webpage and register for the event.
- **Roll-Up banner:** The roll banner sized 850mm x 2000 mm (printed) can be used at the venue for supporting the visual experience that the participants have during the event.
- **SAVE The DATE banner (digital banner):** The digital banner can be used for social media posts and as a featured image in news items on the partner's organization website.

- **Enroll NOW banner:** The digital banner (similar to save-the-date banner) can be used for social media posts and as a featured image in news items on the partner's organization website.
- **Program:** The program of the event which can be either printed or distributed online to whoever is interested in the event.
- **INFO pack:** A promotional material that can be printed and handed out in face-to-face promotional activities. Moreover, it can be sent via email within the partners' networks and provides information about the event, its program and includes the registration link in hyperlinked content.
- **Invitation:** A 1-page material, sized A6, which can be printed easily (with low cost) and handed out in face-to-face activities. It includes a QR code where anyone interested in can scan the code and redirected to the VITALISE website at the dedicated webpage and register for the event.
- **Certificate of attendance for the Summer School 2023:** A 1-page material which "certified" the participation to the Summer School 2023. It was sent online to participants by ENOLL team (WP4 leader)
- **Certificate of attendance for the Commercialization Bootcamp:** A 1-page material which "certified" the participation to the event. It was sent online to participants by Anthology Venture team.

Particularly, in the period **April 2023 – May 2023** the materials produced for the promotion of the event are showcased in the figures that follow.

Figure 32 Summer School 2023 – Save-the-dates Digital Poster

Figure 33 Summer School 2023 – Apply now Digital Poster

Figure 34 Summer School 2023 – Digital Banner

Figure 35 Summer School 2023 - Invitation

Summary

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain will have the opportunity to learn more about the open innovation and Living Lab tools, methods and services to improve their research and follow new scientific paths thanks to the support of the VITALISE high-experienced trainers on the Living Lab methodology. Participants will be also invited to access the VITALISE ICT tools and infrastructure within the project open calls to collaborate on scientific research with Living Labs recognized and labelled by the European Network of Living Labs.

In addition, a Commercialization Bootcamp will be held immediately prior to the Summer School. These two days will focus on a practical approach for researchers and practitioners who are interested in understanding the path to market for new products and services.

The VITALISE Summer School 2023 on Living Labs, is provided by the VITALISE European Commission funded project, which integrates living labs coming from the three major living lab networks in Europe:

- ENOLL, with 130 living lab members around the world, 41% of which are in the health and wellbeing domain.
- Forum LLSA comprised of 38 members, all of which in the health and wellbeing domain.
- EIT Health Living Labs, composed of 56 active Living Labs and an additional 37 that are in the process of joining, all of them in the health and wellbeing domain.

Program Overview

VITALISE Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp		
Day 1	6 June 2023	Full day Bootcamp
Day 2	7 June 2023	Full day Bootcamp & Excursion
Day 3	8 June 2023	Full day Summer School
Day 4	9 June 2023	Half day Summer School until 13:30

Venue

GAIA BILBAO Paseo Uribitearte, 3
3^o 48001 - Bilbao.
Bizkaia - Spain

Registration

Participation is **FREE** of charge but registration is required. [You can register here.](#)

Objectives of the course

- Support European researchers and students
- Contribute towards increasing access of external researchers, outside the VITALISE project.
- Co-create services based on open innovation and Living Lab methodologies together with stakeholders from all over Europe

Aim

The VITALISE 2023 Summer School on Living Labs, aims to provide researchers worldwide effective training both on how to implement the Living Lab methodology in their studies, as well as involve living labs Research Infrastructures and their services in their Health and Wellbeing research studies.

Who can participate?

- Researchers,
- Students,
- Teachers, and
- Living lab beginners

Interested in applying the Living Lab methodology and tools in their academic and business contexts.

Infopack | VITALISE
Summer School 2023

Project Coordinator:
Dr. Evdokia Konstantinidou

Scientific Coordinator:
Prof. Patrick Somers

Summer School Leader:
Dr. Francesca Spagnoli

VITALISE H2020 project

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Figure 36 Summer School 2023– INFOPack (6-pager)

VITALISE SUMMER SCHOOL 2023		VITALISE SUMMER SCHOOL 2023		VITALISE SUMMER SCHOOL 2023		VITALISE SUMMER SCHOOL 2023	
Commercialization Bootcamp Program		Commercialization Bootcamp Program		Summer School Program		Summer School Program	
Day 1 Monday 06 June 2023		Day 2 Wednesday 07 June 2023		Day 3 Thursday 08 June 2023		Day 4 Friday 09 June 2023	
09:30 - 10:00	Welcome	09:30 - 10:00	Assessment tools for commercialisation of biotech	Developing your own research through Living Labs		Putting the life into your Living Lab: VITALISE Tools	
10:00 - 10:30	Business Model Canvas: Successes & Challenges	10:45 - 10:45	Improving Your Intellectual Property Strategy and other issues	Topic 1		Topic 1	
10:30 - 11:00	Scaling up from a PhD project to a real business case: full business Plan	10:45 - 11:00	Investment Goals for Tech Startups: Funding Cycles & Sources	Topic 2		Topic 2	
11:00 - 11:30	Pathways for Commercialisation	11:30 - 11:30	Outfitting	Topic 3		Topic 3	
11:30 - 11:45	Coffee Break	11:45 - 11:45	Local Regulatory Needs: Commercialisation Case Study Discussion & Q/A	Topic 4		Topic 4	
11:45 - 12:00	How to Develop Funding	12:00	Lunch and registration for the afternoon	Topic 5		Topic 5	
12:00 - 12:30	How to Develop Funding			Topic 6		Topic 6	
12:30 - 12:45	How to Develop Funding and commercialisation - Group Working Problem - Solution 1/2			Topic 7		Topic 7	
12:45 - 13:00	Lunch Break			Topic 8		Topic 8	
13:00 - 13:15	Research Models			Topic 9		Topic 9	
13:15 - 13:30	Group Work: Model Development Technical Details			Topic 10		Topic 10	
13:30 - 13:45	Discussion & Reflections			Topic 11		Topic 11	

Figure 37 Summer School 2023 - 4-day program

Figure 38 Summer School 2023 – Poster

Figure 39 Summer School 2023 – Certificate of Attendance

Additionally, VILABS prepared and designed **promotional goodies and giveaways** such as content for **fabric bag** (3 options available to choose), **pen** (2 options available to choose), **lanyards & badges** (3 options available to choose), **notebooks** (4 options available to choose), and **stickers**.

Figure 40 Summer School 2023 – Fabric Bag Design (multiple options)

Figure 41 Summer School 2023 – Lanyards and Badges design (multiple options)

Figure 42 Summer School 2023 – Notebooks (multiple options)

Figure 43 Summer School 2023 - Pens (multiple options)

2.7.3 Open Living Lab Days 2023

For the **Open Living Lab Days 2023** conducted in Barcelona, an ENoLL booth was set to host the VITALISE project along with other EU-funded projects. For this purpose, the Communication manager of VITALISE prepared a **poster** with the relevant info, results, and activities of the project. The poster created was sent for review to the project to ensure its final version accurately represented the project. The figure below displays the ultimate version of the poster.

Figure 44 OLLD 2023 - VITALISE Poster

2.7.4 Pitch Clinic Event

A digital poster for the VITALISE Pitch Clinic Event was created that accompanied the promotional activities for the event, such as social media posts, website blog posts, newsletters, etc. The poster outlined key details about the event, including dates and participation format.

Figure 45 VITALISE Pitch Clinic Event - Poster

2.7.5 VITALISE's Virtual Access to Datasets

The **digital poster** below was designed to promote **VITALISE's Virtual Access to Datasets**, ensuring clear understanding of the essential information to the audience.

Figure 46 VITALISE's Virtual Access to Datasets - Poster

2.7.6 Innovate to thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation

A visually engaging **poster** was also designed to promote the **Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation** webinars.

Figure 47 Innovate to Thrive - Poster

2.7.7 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

For the **Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium**, a range of promotional materials were crafted to disseminate details about the upcoming event. This encompassed the creation of **digital posters, banners, lanyards, and photobooth designs**, all serving as effective promotional tools.

The VITALISE Consortium consistently shared the event poster across their social media platforms to boost awareness and engagement. Furthermore, the banners, lanyards, and photobooth materials were professionally printed and then deployed throughout the event venue, enhancing visibility and fostering a cohesive branding experience for attendees.

Figure 48 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium - Digital Poster

Figure 49 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium - Banner

Figure 50 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium - Lanyards & Badges

Figure 51 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium – Photobooth

2.8 ZENODO Community

Zenodo is a digital repository that allows researchers, scientists, and scholars to securely store, share, and preserve their research outputs. It provides a user-friendly platform where users can upload and publish their datasets, software, preprints, conference papers, and other research artifacts. With its open-access approach, Zenodo promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing within the research community. It also assigns a unique and persistent DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to each uploaded item, ensuring its long-term accessibility and citability.

2.8.1 The VITALISE ZENODO community

The VITALISE project, established its own dedicated [community on Zenodo](#). This initiative aimed to foster an inclusive society by freely sharing all approved public deliverables under open access status. By embracing an open access approach, the project aimed to create an inclusive society and disseminate valuable knowledge and insights for the benefit of all. The VITALISE project’s presence on ZENODO signifies a crucial step towards maximizing the impact of its findings and engaging a

diverse range of stakeholders. By joining the VITALISE community on Zenodo researchers and enthusiasts could stay connected with the latest advancements in Living Labs research infrastructures in health and wellbeing domains.

Figure 52 VITALISE Zenodo community

2.8.2 List of available documents & materials

Within the VITALISE Zenodo community, numerous types of research outputs were shared throughout the project's lifecycle. These included not only public deliverables but also conference papers and events' presentations. By uploading research outputs in various formats, the VITALISE project aimed to disseminate its findings to a wide audience and contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of Living Labs research infrastructures in health and wellbeing domains. These uploaded materials provided valuable insights, methodologies, and results that were accessible to researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike.

Below is the list with the documents that have been uploaded within the specified period of interest:

Table 8 VITALISE Zenodo community - List of documents

No	Title	Publication type	Link
1	Towards a taxonomy for health living lab data collection devices	Conference paper	https://zenodo.org/records/7434350
2	Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework	Conference paper	https://zenodo.org/records/7434406
3	VITALISE D1.1 Project management and quality control plan	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7984759
4	VITALISE D1.2 First version of Ethics and Safety	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985081
5	VITALISE D1.4 Data Management Plan	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985132

6	VITALISE D2.1 Standard Version 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985193
7	VITALISE D2.2 Evaluation process and tools	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985234
8	VITALISE D2.3 Standard Version 2	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985343
9	VITALISE D2.4 Standard Version 3	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985405
10	VITALISE D2.8 First version of user requirements	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7985477
11	VITALISE D3.4 Panel Management_demonstrator	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7989813
12	VITALISE D3.5 VITALISE SDK Manual	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7989909
13	VITALISE D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7989958
14	VITALISE D4.1 and D4.3 online and printed educational	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7989990
15	VITALISE D4.3 Printed educational material	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990050
16	VITALISE D4.7 University Course Design	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990074
17	VITALISE D4.8 Commercialisation Potential of Research	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990106
18	VITALISE D5.2 Ethical application documents for JRA1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990925
19	VITALISE D6.2 Ethical application documents for JRA2	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990941
20	VITALISE D7.2 Ethical application documents for JRA3	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990949
21	VITALISE D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7990963
22	VITALISE D13.2 Dissemination and Communication	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/7993669
23	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium Presentations	Presentation	https://zenodo.org/records/10691430

2.9 Digital Publishing Platform

Digital publishing platforms provide a convenient way to share and access a wide range of information and resources. These platforms foster collaboration, enable individuals to showcase their work, and offer interactive features to enhance the user experience. As part of this initiative, a SlideShare account has been established by the Dissemination manager to store and regularly update project presentations.

SlideShare is an online platform that allows users to share and discover a wide variety of presentations. It serves as a valuable resource for individuals seeking to expand their knowledge in various fields. Users can find slideshows on topics ranging from academic subjects to professional insights, making it a valuable tool for educators, professionals, and enthusiasts alike. With its visually engaging format, SlideShare offers a unique way to present complex ideas and information in a concise and accessible manner.

2.9.1 VITALISE SlideShare

The VITALISE project established its dedicated account on [SlideShare](https://www.slideshare.net), a renowned platform for sharing and accessing presentations. The account serves as a repository of project presentations, freely available to all users, as part of the project's commitment to open access and knowledge dissemination.

The VITALISE SlideShare channel showcased a diverse range of materials, including presentations from the highly anticipated VITALISE 2023 Summer School and Commercialisation Bootcamp and from the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. By following the account on SlideShare, users had the opportunity to stay up to date with the latest presentations and materials from the VITALISE project. This provided them access to a wealth of knowledge and valuable resources that contributed to their understanding of Living Labs, health, and wellbeing.

Figure 53 VITALISE SlideShare channel

Table 9 List of SlideShare documents

No	Title	Publication type	Link
1	Leveraging IP with Research Teams_Bootcamp Bilbao.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/05-leveraging-ip-with-research-teamsbootcamp-bilbaopdf
2	VITALISE Bootcamp - Intro.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/vitalise-bootcamp-intropdf
3	VITALISE bootcamp Startup Successes & Challenges.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/02-vitalise-bootcamp-startup-successes-challengespdf
4	VITALISE Bootcamp - Tools.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/06-vitalise-bootcamp-toolspdf
5	VITALISE bootcamp Revenue Structures.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/07-vitalise-bootcamp-revenue-structurespdf
6	VITALISE Bootcamp - Commercialization Pathway.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/03-vitalise-bootcamp-commercialization-pathwaypdf
7	VITALISE Bootcamp - Investment Basics.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/08-vitalise-bootcamp-investment-basicspdf
8	VITALISE bootcamp Design Thinking & User Analysis.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/04-vitalise-bootcamp-design-thinking-user-analysispdf
9	VITALISE Summer School 2023_DAY 3 FINAL.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/01vitalise-summer-school-2023day-3-finalpdf

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10	VITALISE Summer School 2023_ DAY 4 FINAL.pdf	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/vitalise-summer-school-2023-day-4-finalpdf
11	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium Presentations	Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/health-and-wellbeing-living-lab-symposium-presentations/266987410
12	01.1_Additional material 2-RESEARCH PROTOCOL SYNOPSIS template.docx	Document	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/011additional-material-2research-protocol-synopsis-templatedocx
13	01.2_Additional material-Research Methods & Reporting.pdf	Document	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/012additional-materialresearch-methods-reportingpdf

3 Communication and Dissemination Activities

Effective communication and dissemination activities are essential for maximizing the visibility and impact of any project. In the case of VITALISE, these activities play a crucial role in ensuring that the project's goals, results, and success stories are widely understood and appreciated. By effectively communicating the contributions of VITALISE towards accessible research infrastructures, the project increased its visibility and showcased its significance to relevant stakeholders. Through a well-designed and integrated communication plan, the VITALISE consortium engaged with the target audience and the general public, conveying information in a clear and comprehensible manner. This section focuses on the strategies and efforts undertaken by the consortium to enhance the project's visibility, communicate its outcomes, and engage with stakeholders effectively. The input to this section is based to the Dissemination Activities Report templates that was internally circulated to partners for completion regarding their activities corresponding to each section.

3.1 Organization of VITALISE Events

The VITALISE consortium has organized a series of events during the period of interest to effectively communicate the outcomes of the project. These events have been designed to engage with and involve relevant stakeholders in the dissemination and discussion of the project's findings. Through these organized events, the consortium aims to foster collaboration, exchange knowledge, and promote the utilization of the project's outcomes among key stakeholders.

3.1.1 List of VITALISE Events

Table 10 List of VITALISE Outreach Events

No.	Organization <insert the name of your organization>	Name of the Event	Date of the Event <When>	Location of the Event <City, Country / Online>	Description of the Activity <type of event, activity description, size of the audience, type of the audience>
1	LiCalab	Fast Track Training	2022-2024	In-person in all the hosting Living Labs + online	<p>Audience: All selected TA researchers (academia, entrepreneurs, LL practitioners, master students) Immersion into the world of LL. Different training blocks to be used in a flexible way.</p> <p>Fast Track Training 2022 Training Materials – Vitalise-Project</p> <p>Icebreaker game</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Short introduction into LL – LL services – ethical framework 2. Vitalise - The importance of harmonisation 3. Methodologies (Theory) 4. Methodologies Workshop 5. Target groups – Panel management 6. How to deal with companies – Business model preparation
2	AUTH	Fast Track Training	2022-2024	In-person in all the hosting Living Labs	<p>Audience: All the selected TA researchers/applicants (academia, entrepreneurs, LL practitioners) Immersion into the world of LL. Different training blocks used in a flexible way.</p>
3	All partners	VITALISE Summer School 2023	Jun 6-9, 2023	Bilbao, Spain	The VITALISE Summer School 2023 was a collaborative effort between VITALISE's partners, aimed at delivering a comprehensive and impactful learning experience.

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					The event included project presentation, trainings, demonstrations, researchers engagement, dissemination.
4	UPM	VITALISE Master Course webinars	Oct 16, 2023, Session 2 Oct 25, 2023 Session 4 Dec 13, 2023 Session 8	Online	SESSION 2 EXPLORING THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATION TYPOLOGY AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS: UNLEASHING THE POWER OF COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION: 2nd speaker Irene Mallo, presentation: "From User-Centred Design to implementation science: the journey" SESSION 4 LIVING LABS' FUNDAMENTALS: 4th speaker Beatriz Merino, presentation "Living Lab Business Model, Business Plan and Sustainability" SESSION 8 DRIVING INNOVATION SUCCESS: UNLEASHING THE POWER OF USER-CENTRIC RESEARCH DESIGN FOR YOUR NEXT PROJECT Coordination Module by Beatriz Merino. Course introduction + Final remarks
5	UPM	Fast Track Training	Oct 25, 2023	Madrid, Spain	All selected TA #93 researchers. Immersion in the world of LL. Different training blocks to use flexibly.
6	LiCalab	VITALISE Master Course webinar	31/10/23 & 08/11/23	Online	Session 4 PANEL MANAGEMENT AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT: Explored the benefits and limitations of panel management and the process of establishment and maintenance. Session 5 NEEDS ASSESSMENT AND PROBLEM DEFINITION: Emphasized the critical importance of understanding users' needs before initiating any design process. Attendees learned techniques for empathizing with end-users, distinguishing between needs assessment and analysis, and effectively framing problems by addressing the who, why, what, where, and when aspects.
7	McGill and UdeM	First Canadian Living Labs Summit	Nov 6-7, 2023	Montreal, Canada	Living Lab summit: talks, roundtables, on the topic of LL. The summit united government stakeholders to promote the Living Lab approach, showcasing existing labs in Canada

D13.5 Dissemination and Communication activities report (final version)

					andthe EU. It facilitated networking, knowledge exchange, and the exploration of new collaboration and funding opportunities.
8	McGill and UdeM, ENoLL	ENoLL BOOT CAMP Living Labs	Nov 7-8, 2023	Montreal, Canada	A full training package offered to CRIR students of 3 frontal lessons and 2 hands-on sessions delivered in 2-half days. Training offered by 2 professional senior trainers: Ms. Martina De Sole (Director of ENoLL) and Dr. Francesca Spagnoli (Head of Capacity Building & Research at ENoLL).
9	AUTH	Training on LL principals and methodologies – The example of the VITALISE project	Nov 21, 2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Demonstrations and training on LL principles and methodologies, using the example of the VITALISE project and the material produced for the VITALISE FTTP. -Participants: nine (9) researchers coming from the Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland
10	UPM	Fast Track Training	Nov 29, 2023	Online	All selected TA #59 researchers. Immersion in the world of LL. Different training blocks to use flexibly.
11	McGill	VITALISE Master Course Webinars	Nov 20, 2023 and Dec 4, 2023	Online	SESSION 6 THE “HOW” THE “WHAT” THE “WHEN” AND “WITH WHOM” OF MEASUREMENT IN LIVING LAB RESEARCH: Provided participants with an in-depth exploration of research methodologies relevant to living lab research, focusing on topics such as health and wellbeing. SESSION 7 EMPOWERING COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION: CO-CREATION AND USER TESTING METHODS UNVEILED: Engaged participants in the realm of co-creation and testing methods essential for driving innovation.
12	AUTH	VITALISE Master Course Webinars	Oct 16, 2023 Oct 31, 2023 Dec 5, 2023	Online	Session 2, 4, 7
13	TREBAG	VITALISE Master Course webinar	Oct 31, 2023 & Nov 8, 2023	Online	Session8
14	TREBAG	VITALISE open day for the elderly I	Jan 26, 2024	SELYP, HUngary	Open day for the elderly on VITALISE, the Hungarian JRA activities. Activities and presentations on ageing with invited speakers and facilitators . 66 participants
15	ENoLL	ENoLL Info Day 2024	Jan 19, 2024	Athens, Greece	This event aimed to raise awareness about the significance of Living Labs (LLs) in addressing societal challenges, fostering

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					sustainable development, and showcasing successful LL initiatives in Greece, contributing to the national innovation ecosystem.
16	Anthology Ventures	Pitch Clinic Event	Feb 13, 2024 Feb 15, 2024 Feb 22, 2024	Online	The event aimed to improve researchers' pitching skills and taught them how to captivate investors with impactful research results. Researchers were able to elevate their research, turning innovative ideas into investment success. They enhanced their ability to deliver persuasive research presentations and articulate findings effectively. Additionally, they gained insights into creating enticing presentations for commercialization or monetization strategies. This event facilitated meaningful relationships, as researchers shared collaboration strategies and left lasting impressions on peers and industry professionals.
17	ENoLL and all partners	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Feb 20, 2024	Brussels, Belgium	The event was dedicated in showcasing the outcomes of the VITALISE project. The symposium's primary objective was to engage in collective reflection with the European Commission and relevant stakeholders and beneficiaries of Research Infrastructures. The aim was to discuss and plan the next steps toward a new era where Research Infrastructures are open and actively involve communities as powerful tools for co-research. A second objective was to showcase completed or on-going research conducted within one or more Living Labs. This achieved through an oral presentation or a panel discussion/roundtable to the Symposium.
18	TREBAG	VITALISE open day for the elderly II	Mar 20, 2024	SELYP, HUNGARY	Open day for the elderly on VITALISE, the Hungarian JRA activities. Activities and presentations on ageing with invited speakers and facilitators . cca30 participants

3.1.2 VITALISE Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp

Figure 54 VITALISE Consortium at Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp

The **VITALISE Summer School 2023 and Commercialization Bootcamp** was a highly anticipated event that took place from June 6-9, 2023, at the GAIA premises in Bilbao, Spain. This four-day program offered participants a unique opportunity to enhance their knowledge and skills in two distinct areas: commercialization and the Living Labs methodology.

The first two days of the event were dedicated to the Commercialization Bootcamp. Led by industry experts, participants engaged in a series of **design thinking exercises** and **discussions on revenue models**. They gained practical insights into the process of **bringing new products and services to the market**. Additionally, they had the opportunity to learn about the **challenges of real-life R&D projects** through a presentation by **Idoia Munoz Lizan** from the **ReRemember Me Project**.

The Commercialization Bootcamp continued on the second day with a focus on assessing commercialization potential. **Argyrios Spyridis** from Anthology Ventures provided valuable insights into topics such as **intellectual property maximization and investment basics for tech startups**. **Eduard Guerrero Aiguabella** from Loop Dx presented a case study on **startup commercialization**, further enriching participants' understanding of the subject.

Figure 55 VITALISE Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp

The next two days of the program were dedicated to the VITALISE Summer School. Renowned speakers from various institutions, including ENOLL, McGill University, Laurea University, GAIA, and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, delivered insightful presentations on Living Labs. Topics covered included **the benefits and challenges of Living Labs, innovation through stakeholder engagement, and case studies on stakeholder engagement and co-creation.**

To deepen their understanding of Living Labs, participants engaged in interactive sessions and hands-on group work. They had the opportunity to collaborate with trainers from VITALISE partners, gaining practical knowledge and experience in applying the Living Labs approach. The sessions also provided a valuable opportunity for participants to connect with each other and form meaningful connections with the VITALISE partners.

The event concluded with a closing speech by **Francesca Spagnoli** from ENOLL. The VITALISE Summer School 2023 and Commercialization Bootcamp successfully achieved its goals of providing hands-on training on commercializing innovations and the Living Labs methodology. Participants left the event equipped with practical knowledge on topics such as intellectual property, investment, and case studies. They also gained a deeper understanding of Living Labs terminology and developed valuable connections with fellow participants and industry experts.

3.1.3 Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation

Figure 56 VITALISE Poster for Innovate to Thrive

The "Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation" webinar series successfully took place from October 2023 to December 2023. The series aimed to equip participants with the knowledge, tools, and strategies to effectively manage innovation and collaborative research within the context of Living Labs.

Comprising **eight (8) modules** delivered as individual webinars, the series covered various topics, including transdisciplinary communication and networking strategies, innovation typology and ecosystems, fundamentals of Living Labs, panel management, problem framing and needs assessment, research methodologies and measurement, co-creation and user testing methods, and user-centric research design.

Participants had the flexibility to choose either **individual webinars** based on their specific interests (Option 1) or enrol in the **comprehensive series** (Option 2). The comprehensive option provided additional benefits, such as personalized feedback on a research plan and a certificate of completion. Recordings of the webinars were made available for participants to access any missed sessions.

Each module of the webinar series aimed to provide participants with both theoretical foundations and practical skills related to innovation management, collaborative research, Living Labs approaches, networking, measurement, co-creation, testing, and user-centric design. The sessions incorporated case studies and examples to illustrate concepts and provide real-world insights.

3.1.4 First Canadian Living Labs Summit

Figure 57 VITALISE at First Canadian Living Labs Summit

The **First Canadian Living Labs Summit** was a groundbreaking event that took place in Montreal, Quebec, Canada, on 6-7 November 2024. The event was co-organized by McGill University, Université de Montréal, the Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation (CRIR), the Provincial Adaptation-Rehabilitation Research Network (REPAR), and the European Network Living Labs (ENOLL).

The event brought together Living Labs, innovation partners, strategic partners, and decision-makers from Canada and abroad to exchange ideas and discuss potential collaborations around the Living Lab approach and methodology. Participants had the opportunity to promote Living Labs in Canada and Europe, showcase specific Living Labs, explore networking and knowledge exchange opportunities, and identify new avenues for collaboration, joint activities, and funding.

The summit was a successful gathering that fostered innovation and collaboration in the field of Living Labs.

Figure 58 VITALISE at First Canadian Living Labs Summit

3.1.5 VITALISE Pitch Clinic Event

Figure 59 VITALISE Poster for Pitch Clinic Event

The **Pitch Clinic Event**, organized by Anthology Ventures, aimed to support researchers in effectively conveying the value of their research findings to non-academic audiences such as investors and businesses. The event took place over three days from February 13-22, 2024.

Participants at the Pitch Clinic Event had the opportunity to **enhance their pitching skills** through a combination of workshops, seminars, and presentations. The event covered various topics, including presenting complex scientific research in a simple manner, understanding investor preferences and criteria, navigating the journey from research to product to business, and practicing pitching in front of experienced professionals.

On the first day of the event, which was held on February 13th, there was a seminar focused on **understanding how investors think and what they seek**. Additionally, a workshop provided guidance on mastering persuasive presentations for research-based startups. An interview with an investor shed light on the challenges and rewards of investing in tech transfer startups.

The second day of the event, held on February 15th, centered around providing **support for startups**. A workshop helped participants create clear value propositions for their research. A presentation explained the stages of commercialization and highlighted the support available from the European Innovation Council. An interview with a startup founder shared their experience of successfully taking a project from the lab to the market.

The final event on February 22nd was a group workshop where participants had the opportunity to **present their business concepts** and **receive valuable feedback** from professionals in the field. Benefits of attending the Pitch Clinic Event included exploring pitching techniques, positioning for investment opportunities, networking with industry experts, and highlighting research experience.

3.1.6 ENoLL Info day 2024

Figure 60 ENoLL Info Day 2024 - Poster

In the **ENoLL Info Day 2024**, hosted by Athena Research and Innovation Center on the 19th of January 2024, participants had the opportunity to immerse themselves in a rich program focused on the **certification process of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)** and the **transformative potential of Living Labs as research infrastructures**. The event brought together experts, practitioners, and enthusiasts from various sectors to exchange knowledge, share best practices, and explore innovative approaches to driving research and innovation through Living Labs.

Through a series of keynote presentations, interactive workshops, and panel discussions, attendees gained valuable insights into the benefits and opportunities offered by Living Labs. They learned how Living Labs can serve as collaborative spaces for co-creation, experimentation, and user-centric innovation. The event showcased successful case studies and real-world examples of how Living Labs have facilitated breakthrough solutions across industries such as healthcare, smart cities, mobility, and more.

ENoLL Info Day 2024 fostered meaningful connections and networking opportunities, enabling participants to engage in fruitful discussions with fellow professionals, researchers, and policymakers. The event served as a catalyst for collaboration, sparking new ideas and initiatives that have the potential to drive positive change and shape the future of innovation.

By participating in ENoLL Info Day 2024, attendees gained a deeper understanding of the certification process and the key elements required to establish and operate successful Living Labs. They left the event equipped with practical insights, tools, and frameworks to further enhance their research and innovation practices, leveraging the power of Living Labs.

3.1.7 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

Figure 61 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

The **Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium** took place in Brussels on February 20, 2024 and served as the culminating event for the VITALISE project, showcasing project results and fostering dialogue within the research community. The symposium's primary objective was to **engage in collective reflection with the European Commission and relevant stakeholders and beneficiaries of Research Infrastructures**. The aim was to discuss and **plan the next steps toward a new era** where Research Infrastructures are open and actively involve communities as powerful tools for co-research. A second objective was to **showcase completed or on-going research conducted within one or more Living Labs participating in the VITALISE consortium**. This was achieved through an oral presentation or a panel discussion/roundtable to the Symposium. Furthermore, the VITALISE consortium undertook significant dissemination and communication activities to ensure the success of the Symposium. In particular:

Before the event

During the preparative phase of the Symposium, a dedicated **brand identity** was established for the Symposium, which will be used in the upcoming years of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. An initial digital banner was created, which was used as the basis for the website and social media presence of the event, as well as for the dissemination materials produced for the first Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium such as the presentation template, badges and the photobooth used during the Symposium. Furthermore, a [webpage dedicated to the event](#) was designed and developed on the VITALISE website, where all the information around the Symposium was populated. This sub-page provided essential information such as the date, venue, agenda, and registration details.

Figure 62 HWLL_Symposium webpage

To encourage broad participation, an **Open Call was launched**, inviting researchers utilizing the VITALISE Transnational Access and Virtual Access Service to present their work at the Symposium. Successful applicants received travel funding from the VITALISE project. **A dedicated webpage** on the VITALISE website provided application information.

A **comprehensive dissemination** plan was implemented to reach a wide audience. This included **frequent social media posts** across all project channels using the **hashtag #HWLL_Symposium**, with **additional promotion by VITALISE partners** on their respective networks. To further amplify the Symposium's reach, a targeted email CTA campaign was conducted through the VITALISE mailing list, and the event was listed on the [European Commission's upcoming events page](#).

During the event

During the event, live coverage was provided on X (ex-Twitter) throughout the Symposium, featuring speaker introductions, presentation summaries, and speaker photographs using the hashtag **#HWLL_Symposium**. Additionally, relevant European Commission accounts were tagged to increase reach.

After the event

Following the Symposium, summary posts highlighting key takeaways were published on LinkedIn and Facebook, providing a **social media recap of the event**. Presentations delivered during the Symposium were made **publicly available on the VITALISE website and Zenodo**, the open access repository. Additionally, a **press release** summarizing the Symposium was developed by the VILABS team for dissemination to Greek and international media outlets.

3.2 Participation in Third-party Events

The participation of VITALISE partners at third-party events were of utmost importance to the project's success and progress. These events offered valuable opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking, and collaboration with other experts and stakeholders in the field. By actively engaging in these events, VITALISE partners gained insights, exchanged ideas, and forged partnerships that contributed to the advancement of the project. During this reporting period, the partners actively participated in 12 third-party events in total.

3.2.1 List of events

Table 11 List of VITALISE's Participation in 3rd party events

No.	Organization <insert the name of your organization>	Name of the Event	Date of the Event <When>	Location of the Event <City, Country / Online>	Description of the Activity <type of event, activity description, size of the audience, type of the audience>
1	AUTH - ENoLL	Long-term Sustainability of Small and Mid-scale Distributed RI Projects, ICRI 2022 side event	Oct 19-21, 2022	Brno, Czech Republic	Presentation of VITALISE project
2	AUTH	ICRI 2022 (International Conference on Research Infrastructures)	Oct 19-21, 2022	Brno, Czech Republic	Presentation of VITALISE project, promotional material hand out, Dissemination, Networking
3	UPM	CLAIB&CBEB 2022: IX Congreso Latinoamericano de Ingeniería Biomédica (CLAIB 2022) y el XXVIII Congreso Brasileño de Ingeniería Biomédica (CBEB 2022) Florianópolis, Santa Catarina	Oct 25, 2022	Online	"The Hospital of the Future" Speaker: María Teresa Arredondo Waldmeyer
4	LiCalab	Acsell partner meeting	Nov 9-10, 2022	Antwerp, Belgium	Partner meeting: Time slot reserved for dissemination of the Vitalise Open calls (Powerpoint presentation) A mix of Government and care organisations were present <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scotland = NHS en DHI • Timis = Regional Development Agency • Tübingen = universiteit • Slovenia = regionale accelerator

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					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FVG =Italy= regional development Friuli Venezia Giulia (met name het CEI, Central European initiative) • Denmark = Aalborg university and regionale health hub • Names of the contact persons: Linda Shore, Grant Reilly, Andrea Pavlickova, Donna Henderson, Mathilde Bach Daasbjerg, Bente Koch Pedersen, Rebeka Zerovnik, Sandra Evans, Daniel Bühr, Nicoleta Mirica, Adrian Nagel, Eugen Bota, Sebastian Ștefăniță, Gian Matteo Apuzzo, Gabriele Mingolla
5	Anthology Ventures	European Innovation Council Innovation Summit 2022	Dec 7, 2022	Tour & Taxis, Brussels, Belgium	Networking meeting with EU representatives and health-related startups to discuss the project and the Open Calls. The audience included 5 people from the industry sector and 2 policymakers
6	AUTH	Kick-off Meeting of the Gill Project	Jan 31, 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation & Dissemination of the VITALISE Open calls / Workshop
7	AUTH	Kick-off Meeting of the Managidith Project	Feb 6-7, 2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Dissemination, Networking
8	INTRAS	37th EFPSA Congress Portugal 2023	Mar 27, 2023	Povoa de Varzim, Portugal	Presentation of the VITALISE project.
9	AUTH	1st Hellenic Living Lab summit	Apr 19, 2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Project demonstration
10	AUTH	CSI MEETING	Apr 24, 2023	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Presentation of VITALISE project, promotional material hand out, Dissemination, Networking
11	AUTH	UNICA and the City – UNICA Green and SDGs JOINT CONFERENCE	Apr 25-26, 2023	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Presentation of VITALISE project, promotional material hand out, Dissemination, Networking
12	AUTH	INTEGER project meeting	Mar 29, 2023	Krakow, Poland	Time slot reserved for presenting VITALISE project, dissemination of the Vitalise Open calls (Powerpoint presentation)
13	AUTH - ENoLL	Applied working session: "The role of scientific research and research expertise in Horizon	May 2023	Online	Presentation of VITALISE project

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		Europe projects", West University of Timișoara			
14	INTRAS	ICIC23 Main Programme - IFIC (integratedcarefoundation.org)	May 23, 2023	Antwerp, Belgium	Presentation of the VITALISE project. The 23 rd International Conference on Integrated Care (ICIC23) in partnership with the Flanders Agency for Health and Care and Visit Flanders took place at Flanders Meeting & Convention Center Antwerp, Flanders on 22-24 May 2023. With the overarching theme ' Care in action: how to work together, a participatory approach ', the conference brought together leaders, researchers, clinicians, managers, citizens, patients and caregivers from around the world who are engaged in the design and delivery of integrated health and social care.
15	McGill University	Webinar Horizon 2020 programs	May 31, 2023	Online	Local/national/international event
16	Social IT	We Make Future 2023	Jun 16, 2023	Rimini Fiera, Italy	(Customers, Civil groups, general public) We make Future is an International Trade Fair and Festival on Tech and Digital Innovation. Our company had a booth at this event, and we distributed VITALISE' brochures. The project has received interest from several people who have visited our booth.
17	AUTH	Summer School on Biomedical Data Science (MSc in Biomedical engineering, AUTH)	Jun 27-30, 2023	Chalkidiki, Greece	Project demonstration, promotional material hand out, Accelup platform
18	UPM	IEEE EMBC2023 Workshop.	Jul, 24, 2023	Sydney, Australia	"International Living Labs for Multi-Lateral Collaborations in Health and Wellbeing" Health Monitoring: How Emerging Technologies Can Help? Speaker: María Teresa Arredondo Waldmeyer
19	AUTH	HTWG Konstanz : Medical Summer School - "Towards sustainable and co-designed telemedicine systems in the Western Balkans"	Sept 8, 2023	Tirana, Albania	Presentation of VITALISE project

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20	TREBAG	European Sport Congress	Sept 20-22, 2023	Gijón, Spain	Ms. Eniko Nagy, a representative of the VITALISE project and the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab, earned the title of “Best Oral Communication” at the conference. International sport congress in the research field on sport and health. Vitalise and JRA3 research were presented and was awarded the best oral presentation of the congress. https://sportcongress.eu/eusc-2023/
21	McGill-UdeM	OLLD 2023	Sept 21-23, 2023	Barcelona, Spain	Talk: presentation of the Living Lab Lexicon. Roundtable discussion: Living Lab Harmonization: the journey towards a common language
22	AUTH	ELEVIT2023 (10th Panhellenic Conference on Biomedical Technology)	Oct 6-8, 2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Demonstration, promotional material hand out, poster presentation about the results of the co-creation sessions within the museum project (JRA3)
23	UPM	Seminar: “KEY ENABLING INNOVATIONS- powering the future of human wellbeing” At Khalifa University	Oct 30 - Nov 3, 2023	EAU	More than 10 UPM researchers presented the main lines of research in the field of health and well-being with key technologies such as AI, robotics and data to exchange knowledge, experiences and identify possibilities for synergies Presentation of the VITALISE project and training on Living Labs.
24	AUTH	First Canadian Living Lab Summit	Nov 6-7, 2023	Montreal, Canada	Dissemination, Networking
25	AUTH	AHL Conference 2023	Nov 13-15, 2023	Napoli, Italy	Presentation of VITALISE project, promotional material hand out, Dissemination, Networking
26	UPM	Madrid Science Week	Nov 16, 2023	Madrid, Spain	More than 130 visitors were received in 4 shifts at the LifeSpace Living Lab. In each of the visits, the Living Lab was presented and a demo of the fast training organized for the TAs was carried out, as well as other awareness activities about living labs.
27	TREBAG	ICSE: International Conference on Sports and Education	Nov 24, 2023	Rome, Italy	Participating VITALISE and Hungarian JRA3 activities at the conference online. Online presentation for participants in personal presence in Rome. https://icse-platform.eu/stream/
28	UPM	Madrid Science Week	Dec 2, 2023	Madrid, Spain	More than 60 visitors were received in 2 shifts at the LifeSpace Living Lab. In each of the visits, the VITALISE

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					project was presented, focusing on the JRA2 pilot in Madrid to raise awareness about the importance of living labs for health.
29	TREBAG	EUSPORTSLAB 2023	Dec 8-9, 2023	CONI LOMBARDIA Milan	Participation and networking at the annually organized eusportslab conference and presenting VITALISE in networking event. 70 participants, trainers, facilitators, project managers, stakeholders from the sport and research fields. https://eusportlab.eu/eusportlab-2023/
30	AUTH	ENoLL Info Day 2023	Jan 19, 2024	Athens, Greece	Demonstration, promotional material hand out
31	AUTH	8th Annual Conference of the Hellenic Cancer Federation	Feb 2-4, 2024	Athens, Greece	Presentation of VITALISE project, promotional material hand out, Dissemination, Networking
32	McGill University	Webinar Horizon 2020 programs	Feb. 7, 2024	Online	Local/national/international event

3.2.2 We Make Future 2023

Figure 63 Social IT partners at We Make Future 2023

[We Make Future](#) is a highly anticipated event that brings together individuals, businesses, and organizations from around the world to explore and showcase the latest advancements in technology, digital innovation, and culture. The event serves as a platform for networking, learning, and inspiration.

Our partners from Social IT represented VITALISE at **We Make Future 2023**, that took place on the **16th of June 2023** at **Rimini Fiera in Italy**. With a diverse range of exhibits, workshops, and presentations, We Make Future 2023 provided a unique opportunity for attendees to connect with industry experts, discover cutting-edge solutions, and gain insights into the future of technology and its impact on various sectors.

VITALISE participated in the event with its own booth. The partners seized the opportunity to showcase their groundbreaking research initiatives and cutting-edge solutions at this prestigious event. Throughout the event, the representatives from Social IT actively interacted with attendees, answering questions, providing demonstrations, and distributing relevant brochures and materials. The event provided a valuable platform for VITALISE to engage with experts, stakeholders, and industry leaders, encouraging collaborative discussions and knowledge-sharing.

Figure 64 VITALISE materials at We Make Future 2023

3.2.3 European Sport Congress

Figure 65 TREBAG partner at European Sport Congress

The [European Sport Congress](#) (EUSC) is an international conference focused on the European perspective of sport, the design and implementation of innovative projects, and the internationalisation of sport-related institutions and the mobility of their staff.

The EUSC is an annual itinerant event, facilitating the access of a variety of stakeholders and generating an impact over different European regions over the years.

VITALISE's partner, the TREBAG Intellectual Property and Project Manager, made a significant impact at the European Sport Congress, held from **September 20-22, 2023**, in **Gijón, Spain**.

Ms. Eniko Nagy, a representative of the VITALISE project and the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab, took center stage at the event. The project's communication and Hungarian research findings were selected for a prominent presentation, which subsequently earned the title of "Best Oral Communication" at the conference.

3.2.4 Open Living Lab days 2023

Figure 66 VITALISE at Open Living Lab Days 2023

[Open Living Lab Days 2023](#) took place in **Barcelona, Spain**, on the **21-23 of September 2023**. Organized by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), this event brought together researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders from around the world to discuss the latest trends and developments in the field of Living Labs.

The conference program spanned three days and offered a variety of sessions, workshops, and interactive discussions. It provided a platform for participants to exchange knowledge, share best practices, and collaborate on advancing the Living Lab methodology.

One prominent participant at the conference was the VITALISE project. The VITALISE team, including **Panos Bamidis, Evdokimos Kostantinidis, Despoina Petsani, Teemu Santonen, and Eva Kehayia**, presented on the topic of "**Living Lab Harmonization: the journey towards a common language**". The presentation focused on the efforts of VITALISE to integrate Living Labs into the wider research infrastructure landscape through the process of harmonization. They introduced a harmonization framework and established a roadmap for future work through the creation of a Harmonization Working Group.

During the closing day of the conference, Teemu Santonen from VITALISE received the prestigious **Veli-Pekka Niitamo Best Research Paper award** for his work on "**Towards Living Lab value proposition: Living Lab experts' perceptions on living lab value**". This recognition highlighted the valuable contributions made by the VITALISE project and their dedication to advancing the understanding of Living Lab value propositions.

Figure 67 Teemu Santonen from VITALISE receives the Best Research Paper Award

Overall, Open Living Lab Days 2023 provided a valuable opportunity for participants like VITALISE to connect with others in the Living Lab community. It facilitated discussions on important topics, such as harmonization efforts and the future development of Living Labs. Through this conference, VITALISE and other attendees were able to network, exchange ideas, and collaborate to further align and advance the Living Lab methodology.

Figure 68 VITALISE present at Open Living Lab Days 2023

3.3 Direct Contact with Stakeholders

This section delves into the efforts of the VITALISE Consortium in establishing direct contact with stakeholders. It emphasizes the significance of both face-to-face activities and effective communication with target audiences. Through these direct interactions, the partners aimed to foster collaboration, collect valuable feedback, and cultivate strong relationships with stakeholders. Such endeavors were instrumental in guaranteeing the success and effectiveness of the VITALISE Project.

3.3.1 Face to Face Activities

The face-to-face activities involving direct contact with stakeholders played a crucial role in the success and impact of the VITALISE project. These activities provided a unique opportunity for partners to engage directly with stakeholders, including potential end-users, industry professionals, and policymakers. Through face-to-face interactions, partners gathered valuable feedback, gaining a deeper understanding of stakeholder needs and preferences, while establishing strong relationships. The partners actively participated in a significant number of face-to-face activities during the period of interest, further strengthening their connection with stakeholders and maximizing the project's potential for positive change.

Table 12 List of VITALISE's Face to Face activities

No.	Organization <i><insert the name of your organization></i>	Name and type of the contact <i><Insert the name of the organization you met with and the *type of target audience></i>	Date of the meeting <i><When></i>	Venue/Location of the meeting <i><Where></i>	Activity description <i>(short description of the outcome of the meeting, what we gained from it)</i>
1	AUTH-ENOLL	Co-creation Workshop and Clustering Meeting with Stakeholders from UK, Greece, Estonia, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan	Aug 24-25, 2022	Thessaloniki, Greece	Presentation & Dissemination of the VITALISE Open calls / Workshop, Discussions about the project and the open calls
2	LiCalab	ENoLL OLLD22: conversation with several attendees e.g., Judy Hong Huang, Stavanger, Norway	Sept 20-23, 2022	Turin, Italy	Direct contact during the breaks of the conference. Resulted in 1 TA application (ID20)
3	AUTH	ENoLL OLLD22: conversation with several attendees e.g. Styliani Petroudi from CYENS Centre of Excellence (CoE)	Sept 20-23, 2022	Turin, Italy	Direct contact during the breaks of the conference and the VITALISE existing booth
4	UPM	Meeting with business group G42 Healthcare https://www.g42healthcare.ai/	Oct 17, 2022	EAU	Meeting with a member of the advisory board to present the LifeSpace living lab and the VITALISE project for the analysis of joint opportunities. Several calls and in-person meetings were held.

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5	UPM	Edvolution company, Google service provider with a focus on education https://www.edvolution.es/	Oct 30, 2022	Madrid, Spain	Meeting with CEO and CTO to evaluate options for possible synergies in the field of WP12 and for the perspective of virtual access of the project.
6	LiCalab	Acsell partner meeting: A mix of Government and care organisations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acs • Timis = Regional Development Agency • Tübingen = universiteit • Slovenia = regionale accelerator • FVG =Italy= regional development Friuli VeneziaGiulia (met name het CEI, Central European iinitiative) • Denmark = Aalborg university and regionale health hub Names of the contact persons: Linda Shore, Grant Reilly, Andrea Pavlickova, Donna Henderson, Mathilde Bach Daasbjerg, Bente Koch Pedersen, Rebeka Zerovnik, Sandra Evans, Daniel Bühr, Nicoleta Mirica, Adrian Nagel, Eugen Bota, Sebastian Ștefăniță, Gian Matteo Apuzzo, Gabriele Mingolla	Nov 9-10, 2022	Antwerp, Belgium	Partner meeting: Time slot reserved for dissemination of the Vitalise Open calls (Powerpoint presentation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • + personal contact during the break with several organisations • 1 lead West University of Timisoara (via Sebastian Stefaniga) that resulted in an open call application (ID 36) • 1 applicant from DHI (ID75)
7	Anthology Ventures	Met with startup founder (https://www.themapofcare.com/)	Dec 10, 2022		1:1 Startup Meeting to explain Open Call process - will apply
8	AUTH	Meeting with Laura Smith (University of Leeds), Meeting Purpose: Capacity building for innovation and entrepreneurship	Jan 27, 2023	Leeds, UK	Demonstration, Dissemination, Networking, Discussions about the project and the open calls,
9	AUTH	Researchers from KU Leuven University e.g. Angeliki-Ilektra Karaiskou, Christos Chatzichristos	Feb 1, 2023	Leuven, Belgium	Visit to KU Leuven University/ Direct contact with researchers from the University, discussions about the project and the open calls

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10	UPM	In-person meeting with Business Cluster of Castilla y León https://clustersivi.org/	Mar 1, 2023	Madrid, Spain	Visit to the LifeSpace Living Lab by the Director of the Business Cluster and Project Managers at SIVI to learn about the Living Lab. On the occasion, different opportunities of interest were presented, including VITALISE for carrying out piloting.
11	LiCalab	Aging Fit event, Direct contact with several attendees, e.g., Claire Kemlin & Damien Roche from Tech company Lifebloom, France	Mar 6-7, 2023	Lille, France	Direct contact during the breaks of the conference. Resulted in 1 TA application (ID60)
12	AUTH	Researchers from Jagiellonian University e.g. Monika Jedynak etc.	May 19, 2023	Krakow, Poland	Visit to Jagiellonian University/ Direct contact with researchers from the university, discussions about the project, the open calls and the upcoming summer school – the outcome of the meeting was to schedule a visit to ThessAHALL premises for training and the participation of some researchers to the summer school
13	UPM	Event UPM meet Khalifa University	Jun 28, 2023	Madrid, Spain	Official visit of the head of the Department of Biomedical Engineering at Khalifa University to the UPM. Presentation of the VITALISE project, presentation about transnational access and demo about LifeSpace Living Lab.
14	AUTH	VITALISE presentation to external Living Labs	Jul 1, 2022 Jul 11, 2022	Krakow, Poland	Promote the VITALISE activities in Living Labs that are external to VITALISE consortium, Networking
15	UPM	Event UPM meet Florianopolis University	Jul 11, 2023	Madrid, Spain	Official visit of the Director of the Department of Biomedical Engineering at Florianopolis University to the UPM. Presentation of the VITALISE project, presentation about transnational access and demo about LifeSpace Living Lab.
16	AUTH	ENoLL OLLD23: conversation with several attendees	Sept 21-23, 2023	Barcelona, Spain	Direct contact during the breaks of the conference

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17	AUTH	Meeting with Prof. Sylvain Baillet, McGill University	Nov 7, 2023	Montreal, Canada	Dissemination, Networking, Discussions about the project and the open calls
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3.3.2 Communication with target audiences

The consortium of the VITALISE project has actively engaged with various target audiences to promote and inform about project actions. These efforts have involved personal emails, online meetings, and direct communication with stakeholders from academia, industry, and Living Labs. The aim has been to reach a broad audience and raise awareness about the project's activities and opportunities. Through these interactions, the consortium has sought to encourage participation, gather valuable insights, and foster collaborations.

More specifically, in the academic sphere, VITALISE partners have connected with **professors, researchers, and universities across Europe**. They personally reached out to these individuals through emails, sharing updates about the project's activities, such as the second open call and the info day. The aim was to not only inform them about the opportunities available but also to encourage them to spread the word among their networks. By forging these personal connections, the consortium hoped to attract a wide range of applicants and foster a vibrant research community.

The consortium also made a point of engaging with industry leaders and organizations in various sectors. They sent personalized emails to **digital health and care innovation centers, Living Labs, and industry experts**. These communications served as introductions to the project and provided a platform for exploring potential collaborations. By organizing online meetings, the consortium had the opportunity to dive deeper into discussions, exchanging ideas and insights for application in the open call. These interactions paved the way for valuable partnerships and mutually beneficial outcomes.

Additionally, the VITALISE partners actively connected with **healthcare institutions and clinical research units**. Through online meetings and emails, they communicated the Transnational Access (TA) opportunities available within the project. The goal was to encourage participation and facilitate the integration of the project's activities into the validation processes of these institutions. These efforts enabled the selection and validation of TA projects in close collaboration with healthcare professionals and researchers.

Appendix 1 provides a more comprehensive view of the consortium's communication efforts. It provides a detailed account of each interaction, including dates, organizations contacted, and the purpose of each communication. The outcomes of these actions, such as the submission of applications, exploration of collaboration opportunities, and the dissemination of project information, are also briefly described.

3.4 Collaboration with other projects

The VITALISE consortium by actively engaging with other relevant initiatives, has been able to leverage shared knowledge, resources, and expertise, ultimately enhancing the impact of the project. Through these collaborations, VITALISE has fostered a spirit of innovation and cooperation, facilitating the exchange of best practices, lessons learned, and novel ideas. The project has actively participated in collaborative efforts with multiple projects, resulting in fruitful partnerships and the collective advancement of research and development in the field.

3.4.1 List of projects

Table 13 List of other EU-Funded projects collaborated with VITALISE

No.	Partner's Name <insert the name of your organization>	Name of the project you collaborated with <Project>	Contact person or organization <Organization contacted>	Date <When>	Description of the collaboration activity <Description>
1	AUTH	INADVANCE project	INADVANCE consortium partners	2022	Liaison of InAdvance project & VITALISE project – co-creation session held for VITALISE WP6 during INADVANCE consortium meeting and shared at social media accounts
2	AUTH	FOR21 project	FOR21 consortium partners	2022	Liaison of FOR21 project & VITALISE project – co-creation session held for VITALISE WP6 during FOR21 consortium meeting and shared at social media accounts
3	UPM	PromenAID at Human Brain Project	Project Coordinator, UPM	March, 2023	Several meetings were held to coordinate the implementation of the PromenAID project pilot at LifeSpace Living Lab. For this purpose, VITALISE was presented since Fast Training Program was carried out on April 27 following the model developed for the VITALISE TAs.
4	UPM	VOJEXT Project-H2020	General Coordinator in the Project	Nov-Dec, 2023	Several meetings were held to coordinate the implementation of the VOJEXT project pilot at LifeSpace Living Lab. For this purpose, VITALISE was presented and the Fast Training Program will be carried out in March 2024 following the model developed for the VITALISE TAs.
5	VILABS	Gendered Innovation Living Labs (GILL)	Project Coordinator of GILL, ENoLL	July, 2023	Established a cross-communication synergy to promote both projects' activities.
6	ENoLL	BIO-STREAMS	Project Coordinator, ICCS	February, 2024	Established a cross-communication synergy to promote both projects' activities.

3.5 Press / Media Coverage

Press and media coverage and effective communication with target audiences have been vital aspects of the VITALISE project. This engagement has allowed for the dissemination of project updates, milestones, and relevant information to the target audiences, fostering awareness and understanding. Additionally, media coverage has played a crucial role in raising the project's visibility and showcasing its impact to a wider audience. Also, partners have actively utilized their own communication channels to share project updates, progress, and outcomes, amplifying the reach and impact of VITALISE.

3.5.1 Third-party references to the VITALISE project

The VITALISE project has garnered attention from various external sources, reflecting its significance in the realms of research, technology, and societal impact. This section delves into notable mentions of the project in diverse media platforms, underscoring its collaborative nature and contributions to advancing innovation.

No.	Organization <i><insert the name of your organization></i>	Type of press item <i><press release, interview, etc.></i>	Title of press item <i><When></i>	Media where it was published	URL (if available)
1	AIT	Press release in newspaper (Reached 65.000 people)	"Forschung muss in die Wildnis hinaus"	Austrian Newspaper "Die Presse"	link
2	AUTH	Blog post in Open Knowledge Greece website (okfn.gr)	"Επίσημη έναρξη της υπηρεσίας Εικονικής Πρόσβασης (Virtual Access) στα Δεδομένα!"	Open Knowledge Foundation Website	link
3	TUE	News-item at project's website	Advancing Research Infrastructure: Insights from the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	BIO-STREAMS website	link
4	ENoLL	Social media post	#highlycitedpaper	Electronics MDPI account on LinkedIn	link
5	SLIMMER LEVEN	Social media post	2nd Open Call	LinkedIn	link
6	SLIMMER LEVEN	News item	"2e Open Call VITALISE-project"	Website	link

3.5.1.1 Press release in the Austrian Newspaper "Die Presse"

VITALISE partners from AIT mediated the publication of a press release in the **Austrian newspaper**, named **"Die Presse"** featuring the VITALISE project. The article, titled **"Forschung muss in die Wildnis hinaus"** (Research must go out into the wilderness), discusses the importance of engaging end-users in the development process of new technologies. It emphasizes the concept of Living Labs, where innovations are tested and refined in real-world environments before being fully implemented. The mention of the VITALISE project underscores the broader relevance of this approach to various research endeavours, ultimately emphasizing the collaborative and iterative nature of technology development in contemporary contexts.

Figure 69 VITALISE features in the Austrian Newspaper "Die Presse"

3.5.1.2 VITALISE at BIO-STREAMS project website

VITALISE project featured on a [news-item](#) published in the BIO-STREAMS project website highlighting its participation in the "Health and Wellbeing Symposium" organized by the VITALISE Consortium together with ENOLL in February 2024.

BIO-STREAMS project involved in advancing discussions and initiatives surrounding obesity research and management. Represented by Prof. Izidor Mlakar from the University of Maribor and Lars Munter from the Komiteen for Sundhedsoplysning, BIO-STREAMS actively participated in a panel discussion focused on Childhood and Adolescence Health within Living Labs.

The partnership between BIO-STREAMS and VITALISE is driven by a shared goal of advancing research and innovation in the field of health.

Figure 70 VITALISE at BIO-STREAMS website

3.5.1.3 Highly Cited Paper

The VITALISE paper, titled "Incorporation of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques within a Controlled Data Processing Workflow in the Health and Wellbeing Domain," has been referenced as a highly cited paper on the Electronics MDPI LinkedIn account. This paper, published in the international, peer-reviewed, and open access journal Electronics, focuses on the science of electronics and its applications published semi-monthly online by MDPI.

With its recognition as a highly cited paper, the VITALISE paper has made a significant impact on advancing research and development in the health and wellbeing domain.

Figure 71 VITALISE Highly Cited Paper

3.5.2 Communication Activities in partners channels

VITALISE partners use their network and social media channels to facilitate the dissemination of the project and its activities. Partners reshare the communication material created by the communication manager or produced their own, helping the project achieve more prominent visibility. All project partners put an effort into communicating VITALISE activities through their social media channels and official websites.

More specifically, more than 160 posts on their social media channels and website were created during this time. In Appendix 2 the list of the posts made along with the specific links is included.

3.6 Publications

During the project's lifecycle, as project activities progressed and drew from the previous and newly created knowledge of the project partners, a series of scientific articles were published in the international scientific literature. All partners acknowledged their shared interest in publishing the acquired knowledge to gain recognition and contribute to the advancement of the field's state of knowledge. Particularly, when the content of the publications resulted from the collective efforts of the Consortium or a specific subgroup of partners, the names of the respective individuals and partner organisations were included in the publications.

VITALISE Consortium, during the whole project's lifecycle, have successfully submitted 15 scientific papers in total. Particularly, in the period M19-M36, 7 scientific papers have been submitted and 1 is planned to be submitted at the end of March 2024.

3.6.1 List of publications

Table 14 List of VITALISE Publications

No.	Title of publication <i><in case of joint publication with other partner please mention – [joint]></i>	Date of publication <i><When></i>	Name of Authors (s)	Journal, Publishing house <i><please provide URL/DOI if available></i>	Status <i><accepted/submitted/presented to the conference proceedings and scientific journals></i>
1	Towards living lab value proposition: Living lab experts' perceptions on living lab value Joint publication	2023	Santonen, T., Petronikolou, S., Petsani, D., Dimitriadis, S., Bamidis, P. and Konstantinidis, E.	Proceedings of the Open Living Lab Days Conference 2023 European Network of Living Labs	Published
2	Innovation through the Quintuple Helix in living labs: lessons learned for a transformation from lab to ecosystem	2023	Beatriz Merino-Barbancho, Patricia Abril Jiménez, Irene Mallo, Ivana Lombroni, Gloria Cea, Cristina López Nebreda, María Fernanda Cabrera, Giuseppe Fico, María Teresa Arredondo	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/public-health/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1176598/full	
3	Effect of incorporating metadata to the generation of synthetic time series in a healthcare context	Jun 22, 2023	Imanol Isasa, Mikel Hernandez, Gorka Epelde, Francisco Londoño, Andoni Beristain, Ane Alberdi, Panagiotis Bamidis, Evdokimos Konstantinidis	https://doi.org/10.1109/CBM558004.2023.00341	Presented, and withing conference proceedings
4	Designing a Master course curriculum for Innovation through Living Labs	Sept 27-29, 2023	Diamantis Konstantinos, Konstantinidis Evdokimos, SantonenTeemu, Kehayia Eva, Petsani Despoina, Desole	EAI TIE 2023 - 4th EAI International Conference on Technology, Innovation,	Conference Proceedings

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			Martina, Spagnoli Francesca, Bamidis Panagiotis	Entrepreneurship and Education	
5	“Fostering Wellbeing: Co-Creation Sessions for Enhanced Museum Experiences Among Older Adults”	Oct 6-8, 2023	Vasileia Petronikolou, Despoina Petsani, Eva Kehayia, Nancy Azevedo, Eleni Manakidou, Dimitris Panagiotakos, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Panagiotis Bamidis	10th Panhellenic Conference on Biomedical Technology	Poster presentation/ included in the conference proceedings
6	Comparative Assessment of Synthetic Time Series Generation Approaches in Healthcare: Leveraging Patient Metadata for Accurate Data Synthesis	Jan 30, 2024	Imanol Isasa, Mikel Hernandez, Gorke Epelde, Francisco Londoño, Andoni Beristain, Xabat Larrea, Ane Alberdi, Panagiotis Bamidis, Evdokimos Konstantinidis	https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-024-02427-0	Published in scientific journal (BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making)
7	The impact of multitasking on the comprehension, logical coherence, and retention of stimuli in postgraduate biomedical students	March 4-6, 2024 Velencia (Spain)	S. Malaescu, C. Chiorean, V. Petronikolou, A. Anagnostopoulou, D. Petsani, K. Tagaras, K. Mitsopoulos, P. Antoniou, P. Bamidis, E. Konstantinidis	INTED 2024 (18th International Technology, Education and Development Conference)	
8	Data Publishing and Access Service for Sensitive Data from Living Labs: Enabling Collaboration with External Researchers through Shareable Data	Submitted	Mikel Hernandez, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Gorke Epelde, Francisco Londoño, Despoina Petsani, Michailis Timoleon, Andoni Beristain, Vicky Fiska, Lampros Mpaltadoros, Ilias Machairas, Christoniki Maga-Nteve, Stefanos Vrochidis, Edwin Dokla, Naiara Aginako and Panagiotis Bamidis	Submitted to Big Data and Cognitive Computing (IF=3.7)	Submitted

4 Conclusions

This document constitutes a report of the communication and dissemination activities made by the VITALISE consortium within the period from October 2022 to March 2024 (M19-M36). The communication tools and channels are also outlined. The actions described within this report were planned in deliverables D13.1 and D13.2 which respectively submitted in June 2021 (M3) and October 2022 (M18).

Through the utilization of various communication tools and channels, including the project website, social media accounts, newsletters, and press releases, the project successfully reached and engaged target audiences. The organization of events such as the VITALISE Summer School and the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium further facilitated stakeholder participation and collaboration. Direct contact with stakeholders, collaboration with other projects, and media coverage also contributed to the project's visibility and success. The collective efforts of the 19 European partners from 11 different countries involved in the project played a crucial role in coordinating and amplifying the dissemination and communication activities.

Overall, this document serves as a comprehensive account of the progress, outcomes, and key takeaways of the VITALISE project's dissemination and communication efforts, providing valuable insights for future projects and initiatives.

Appendices

Appendix 1

This list below outlines a summary of the communication activities carried out by the consortium to engage target audiences about the project through various channels, including email, social media, phone calls, website contact forms, etc.

Table 15 List of Consortium's Communication Activities with Target Audience

No.	Organization <i><insert the name of your organization></i>	Name and type of the contact <i><Insert the name of the organization you met with and the *type of target audience></i>	Date of the communication <i><When></i>	Reason of communication <i><Why></i>	Activity description <i><short description of the outcome of the communication, what we gained from it></i>
1	SIT	Sent personal emails to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the 11 External evaluators that are collaborating with us for the scientific evaluation 12 professors/researchers from 8 different universities/research centers spread across Europe 	10/10/2022	2nd Open Call	Personal email for informing about the 2nd OC and about the Info day we had planned. Moreover, we asked to share this opportunity with other interested people.
2	LiCalab	Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre (dhi-scotland.com) Living lab e.g., Janette Hughes, Melanie Hodge, Karim Mahmoud, Marie Simpson, Evans, Sandra, Jay Bradley, Linda Shore, Sonya Lizbeth Joseph, Donna Henderson,	17/01/2023	3rd Open Call TA	Personal email sent on 17/1/23. An exploratory call on January 24 with two employees of the LL about possible topics for application in the open call, and a second call on 30/3/23: 1 application was submitted for LiCalab (ID75) and 1 for UPM (ID59).

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3	LiCalab	Silesian University of Technology in Poland Politechnika Śląska (polsl.pl) Academia e.g., Anna Timofiejczuk	27/1/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, no response received.
4	LiCalab	Anglia Ruskin University University courses at ARU Anglia Ruskin University - ARU Academia e.g., Pamela Knight-Davidson	16/2/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, no response received.
5	LiCalab	Netwell Casala - Dundalk Institute of Technology www.netwellcasala.org Living lab E.g., Oonagh Giggings, Suzanne Smith, Julie Doyle	15/2/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Online meeting, follow up call on 23/3/23. 2 applications were submitted for Transnational Access.
6	LiCalab	Lifebloom Industry e.g. Damien Roche, Claire Kemlin	6/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, online meeting on 20/3/23 and 27/3/23. 1 application submitted for Transnational Access.
7	LiCalab	Koios Care https://www.koios.care Industry e.g., Dimitris Iakovakis, Konstantinos Kyritsis	22/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email after lead from Evdokimos Konstantinidis (AUTH), online meeting on 28/3/23. 1 application submitted for Transnational Access.
8	LiCalab	TUE Eindhoven Eindhoven University of Technology (tue.nl) Academia e.g. Pieter Van Gorp, master students/PhD students	27/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Online meeting after lead from Pieter Van Gorp (TUE). No application submitted.

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9	LiCalab	Xander Tech, augmented reality Xander Industry e.g., Alex Westner	17/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, no response received.
10	LiCalab	associated professor with PhD students Robotics and Nonlinear Control (utcluj.ro)	14/2/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, no response received.
11	LiCalab	www.medsens.io Industry	31/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email after lead from our first TA visitor (ID20), no response received.
12	LiCalab	AI for sound - university of surrey AI4S (surrey.ac.uk) Academia e.g., Thomas Deacon, Mark Plumbley, David Frohlich, etc.	4/4/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, with follow up calls on 6/4/23 and 26/4/23. 1 application submitted for Transnational Access.
13	LiCalab	Fraunhofer Homepage Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft Academia (Lead by Thomas More Lector Lieven De Maesschalck)	14/3/2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Personal email, no response received.
14	LiCalab	Contacting partners from the CrossCare project Flemish partners: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZorgLab Aalst (provincie Oost-Vlaanderen) • Happy Aging (provincie Vlaams-Brabant & Limburg) • Eerstelijnszone Brugge in samenwerking met de POM-West-Vlaanderen (provincie West-Vlaanderen). Dutch partners: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care Innovation Center (provincie Noord-Brabant) • Zuyd Hogeschool/EIZT (provincie Limburg) • Slimmer Leven & Brainport Development (provincie Noord-Brabant) HZ University of Applied Sciences (provincie Zeeland).	February - March 2023	3 rd Open Call TA	Dissemination of the TA open calls through email. No applications resulted from these actions.
15	LiCalab	University of Basel https://virtualbasel.ch/	March 23	3 rd Open Call TA	Lead via our Mobilab & Care partners Bert

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		Academia Joanna Timiliotis			Bonroy and Glen Debard. Emails + online meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 application (ID61), unfortunately cancelled due to health-related issues of the head researcher involved.
16	McGill and UdeM	Contacts in Vienna, Frankfurt, Budapest, Brussels, Ljubljana	Sept. 2022 to Oct 2023	First and second open calls	Direct emails to potential TA applicants
17	McGill and UdeM	Montreal, nationally and internationally	Sept.-Nov. 2023	First Canadian Summit on Living Labs	McGill Research at SPOT newsletter to advertise
18	McGill and UdeM	CRIR	Sept-Oct 2023	First Canadian Summit on Living Labs	CRIR newsletter and LinkedIn to advertise
19	McGill and UdeM	Living Labs across Quebec and Canada	June-July	First Canadian Summit on Living Labs	Direct emails to invite LLs to participate in the summit
20	McGill and UdeM	Nationally/internationally	May 2023	Vitalise/ Horizon2020 programs	Webinar organized by McGill U.

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21	McGill and UdeM	CRIR		May 2022 and May 2023	Vitalise LL Summer Schools	CRIR newsletter and LinkedIn to advertise (both years)
22	McGill and UdeM	AGE-WELL EPIC Conference 2022 (session on Living Labs)		June 2022	Vitalise LL Summer School 2022	Advertised the 2022 summer school at the end of my talk
23	McGill and UdeM	CRIR		Sept-Oct 2023	Vitalise Masters course Webinars	CRIR newsletter and LinkedIn, CRIR student Facebook page to advertise
24	McGill and UdeM	McGill		Sept-Oct 2023	Vitalise Masters course Webinars	McGill Research at SPOT newsletter to advertise
25	UPM	San Carlos Clinical Hospital · Research Unit https://www.comunidad.madrid/hospital/clinicosancarlos/profesionales/investigacion		Jul-Sept 2023	VITALISE TAs	Several online meetings and emails with VITALISE materials to be incorporated as a unit for the validation of TA projects selected by UPM.
26	UPM	HM Private Hospitals of Madrid https://www.hmhospital.com/		Jul-Sep 2023	VITALISE TAs	Several online meetings and sending of material about VITALISE to conduct a face-to-face interview for the TAs selected by UPM.
27	UPM	EIT Health Programme: User Validation Labs: Test your innovation with your end users https://eithealth.eu/programmes/ulabs/		Jun – Nov 2023	VITALISE TA	Several phone calls with Manager Program were made and the VITALISE

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					material was sent to disseminate the open calls and analyse the interest in signing a Memorandum of Understanding.
28	UPM	EIT Health - Spain CLC https://eithealth.eu/in-your-region/spain/	Sep – Nov 2023	MOU	Several phone calls with Spain CLC Director. The VITALISE project material was sent to analyse the interest in signing a Memorandum of Understanding.
29	UPM	EIT Health Programme: User Validation Labs: Test your innovation with your end users	12 th Sep 2023	Open Call TA	Participation in a matchmaking meeting to present VITALISE project and the open call.
30	SIT	Personal email to 14 professors/researchers from 11 different universities/research centers spread across Europe	9 Feb 2024	Pitch Clinic Event	We share the chance to attend the Pitch Clinic Event, asking to share the email with their network of researchers and start-up founders.
31	AUTH	E-mail to the consortium of the LifeChamps –Horizon 2020 project	Oct 25, 2022	2nd Open Call	Disseminate the VITALISE Open Call opportunity. No applications resulted from this action
32	AUTH	E-mail to the consortium of the URBANOME –Horizon 2020 project	Oct 14, 2022	2nd Open Call	Disseminate the VITALISE Open Call

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					opportunity. No applications resulted from this action
33	AUTH	E-mail to the consortium of the SHAPES –Horizon 2020 project	Oct 14, 2022	2nd Open Call	Disseminate the VITALISE Open Call opportunity. No applications resulted from this action
34	AUTH	Communication with Cluster Saude de galicia	June 2023	Promotion of LL Harmonization processes	e-mail followed by a call
35	TREBAG	Anna Lipert <anna.lipert@umed.lodz.pl>	Throughout 2023	TA information and invitation	The University of Lodz was contacted to be provided information about Vitalise and send invitation to participation to TA.
36	TREBAG	Efstathios Christodoulides <EChristodoulides@uclan.ac.uk>	Throughout 2023	TA information and invitation	The UCLAN University of Cyprus was contacted to be provided information about Vitalise and send invitation to participation to TA.
37	TREBAG	Marc Sarens marc.sarens@vub.be	Throughout 2023	TA information and invitation	The University of Brussels-VUB was contacted to be provided information about Vitalise and send invitation to participation to TA.
38	TREBAG	Jose Fernandez Garcia icfg@uma.es	Throughout 2023	TA information and invitation	The University of MALAGA- was contacted to be

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					39provided information about Vitalise and send invitation to participation to TA.
39	TREBAG	Jose Amoroso jose.amoroso@ipleiria.pt		Throughout 2023	TA information and invitation The Leira Politecnica School was contacted to be provided information about Vitalise and send invitation to participation to TA.

Appendix 2

The list below features items related to VITALISE that are highlighted on partners' communication channels, such as their official websites, social media accounts, newsletters, etc.

Table 16 List of References in Partners' Channels

No.	Organization <i><insert the name of your organization></i>	Type of press item <i><press release, interview, etc.></i>	Title of press item <i><When></i>	Media where it was published	URL (if available)
1	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Launch of the 2nd Open Call + Info Day	LinkedIn	link
2	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	Twitter	link
3	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	LinkedIn	link
4	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	Facebook	link
5	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	Twitter	link
6	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	LinkedIn	link
7	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Plenary meeting Vienna	Facebook	link
8	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	VITALISE Info Day	Twitter	link
9	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	VITALISE Info Day	LinkedIn	link
10	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	VITALISE call for External Evaluators - EXTENDED	Twitter	link
11	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	VITALISE call for External Evaluators - EXTENDED	LinkedIn	link
12	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	VITALISE call for External Evaluators - EXTENDED	Facebook	link
13	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	ChatterGlove – an exoskeleton for hearing impaired individuals	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link

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			Chatterglove: een exoskeloton voor doven		
14	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise: 19 European living labs build on living lab standards and procedures	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
15	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise Summer School: how to apply the Living Lab methodology in research	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link
16	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise First open call for free Transnational Access to research infrastructures	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link
17	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise Summer School: how to apply the Living Lab methodology in research	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
18	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	VITALISE provides access to datasets for researchers in the field of health	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
19	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	VITALISE organises a second Bootcamp and Summer School in Spain	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link link old website - still available
20	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise Don't miss our Summer School in Greece	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link old website - still available
21	LiCalab	publication	Vitalise: use cases on transition of acute care	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
22	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	VITALISE Bootcamp & Summer School registration	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
23	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise: LiCalab welcomes first international visitors	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Link old website - still available Dutch link
24	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise partners meet again in Madrid	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link

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25	LiCalab	Project description	Vitalise (Horizon 2020). European cooperation to harmonise procedures for living labs in the field of health and well-being	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
26	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise Second Open Call for free Transnational Access to the Research I	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
27	LiCalab	Publication	[Vitalise] Revalidatie Ondersteund door Technologie: Protocol voor een internationaal 'co-creatie en gebruikerservaring'-onderzoek	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
28	LiCalab	Blog post on two publications	H2020-project Vitalise publiceert twee use cases	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
29	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	VITALISE organises a second Bootcamp and Summer School in Spain VITALISE organiseert tweede Bootcamp en Summer School in Spanje	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link Dutch link Dutch link old website - still available
30	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise-partners ontmoeten elkaar voor de tweede keer in Oostenrijk Vitalise consortium meets a second time in Austria	Thomas More – LiCalab website	Dutch link link old website - still available
31	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Laatste kans om onderzoek te doen in infrastructuur van VITALISE-partners (3 rd open call)	Thomas More – LiCalab website	Dutch link link old website - still available
32	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise: partners ontmoeten elkaar in Finland	Thomas More – LiCalab website	Dutch link

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33	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post	Vitalise in actie	Thomas More – LiCalab website	Dutch link
34	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post: highlighting a collaboration with an external researcher (TA)	[In de kijker] Thomas Deacon - AI for Sound (AI4S)	Thomas More – LiCalab website	Dutch link
35	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post:	[Call] Present your research at the first Health & Wellbeing LL symposium	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
36	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post save the date	Health & wellbeing living lab symposium	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
37	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post: highlighting a collaboration with an external researcher (TA)	[In the picture] Oonagh Giggins - NetwellCASALA	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
38	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post: highlighting TA research	Menopausal women and their physical activity	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
39	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post: highlighting TA research	Barriers to using digital health applications mapped with Lego Serious Play	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
40	LiCalab	Newsletter + Blog post: highlighting a collaboration with an external researcher (TA)	[In the picture] Judy Huang - Ph.D. candidate at the University of Stavanger	Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
41	LiCalab	Social media Call for participants JRA Pro-Self study:	[GEZOCHT] (Bijna) met pensioen? Niets moet, maar een app testen mag!	Facebook	link

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		healthy participants close to retirement or within 3 years after retirement			
42	LiCalab	Social media Call for participants: Parkinson patients and informal care givers (TA ID56)	Gezocht: mensen met Parkinson en hun mantelzorgers voor workshop over applicatie voor betere opvolging en zorg.	Facebook	
43	LiCalab	Social media Call for participants: Deaf or hearing impaired individuals (TA ID36)	LiCalab/Thomas More zoekt doven voor onderzoek met exoskeloton Chatterglove	Facebook	
44	LiCalab	Social media Call for participants: healthy older adults (TA ID20)	[GEZOCHT] Deelnemers voor workshops met Noorse doctoraatsstudente	Facebook + Thomas More – LiCalab website	link
45	LiCalab	Social media post	REGISTER now for symposium on LIVING LAB research on 20th FEBRUARY (Brussels)	LinkedIn	link
46	LiCalab	Social media post TA research (ID72)	Sound wellbeing tested	LinkedIn	link
47	LiCalab	Social media post TA research (ID57-58)	Two researchers from Dundalk Institute of Technology in Ireland visited LiCalab during the #Transnational Access of VITALISE H2020 Project.	LinkedIn	link

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48	LiCalab	Social media post TA research (ID36)	Last week, we had the opportunity to host researchers from West University of Timisoara during the #transnationalaccess of VITALISE H2020 Project.	LinkedIn	link
49	LiCalab	Social media post (TA ID 36)	Wist je dat de ChatterGlove 🤖 gebarentaal omzet in gesproken taal of geschreven tekst?	LinkedIn Thomas More research	link
50	LiCalab	Social media post (TA ID 57)	Dr. Giggins studies the impact of #menopause on quality of life.	LinkedIn	link
51	LiCalab	Blog post	ChatterGlove – an exoskeleton for hearing impaired individuals	Vitalise website	link
52	LiCalab	Blog post	Physical Activity and Physical Function in Mid-Life Women	Vitalise website	link
53	LiCalab	Blog post	Using digital health and wellbeing technologies: bother or burden?	Vitalise website	link
54	LiCalab	Blog post	Sound Wellbeing in Later Life: Exploring wellbeing through contextual understanding of sound and sonic reminiscence	Vitalise website	link
55	McGill and UdeM	Advertisement of summer schools (2022 and 2023)		CRIR website, newsletter and LinkedIn page	
56	McGill	Advertisement of First Canadian Summit of Living Labs		McGill Research at SPOT newsletter to advertise	
57	McGill and UdeM	Advertisement of First Canadian Summit of Living Labs		CRIR website, newsletter and LinkedIn page	
58	McGill	Advertisement of LL Bootcamp		McGill Research at SPOT newsletter to advertise	
59	McGill and UdeM	Advertisement of LL Bootcamp		CRIR website, newsletter and LinkedIn page	

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60	McGill	Advertisement of masters course		McGill Research at SPOT newsletter to advertise	
61	McGill	Advertisement of masters course		CRIR website, newsletter and LinkedIn page	
62	UPM	Advertisement of masters course	Webinar Series on Living Labs - Organized by ENoLL and the VITALISE Project - H2020	Escuela de Ingenieros de Minas y Energía de la UPM	Link
63	UPM	Social Media Post	Advertisement of masters course	LifeStech Research Group LinkedIn	Link
64	UPM	Internal Mailing	Advertisement of masters course	UPM	The Communication Department of the Rectorate of the UPM sent an email to the mass mailinglist with the information on the Master Course promotion (6/10/2023)
65	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Call for external evaluator – Deadline extended	Facebook	Link
66	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Call for external evaluator – Deadline extended	Twitter	link
67	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Call for external evaluator – Deadline extended	Linkedin	link
68	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	3 rd Open Call	Linkedin	link
69	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	3 rd OC – Deadline extended	Facebook	link
70	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	3 rd OC – Deadline extended	Twitter	link
71	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	3 rd OC – Deadline extended	Linkedin	link
72	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	5 th meeting of the VITALISE Harmonization Board	Linkedin	link
73	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Project meeting in Madrid	Linkedin	link

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74	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Virtual Access opportunity	Linkedin	link
75	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Pitch Clinic Event	Twitter	link
76	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Pitch Clinic Event	Linkedin	link
77	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	We Make Future 2023	Linkedin	link
78	VILABS	Social media post	VITALISE Summer School 2023	LinkedIn	link
79	VILABS	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	LinkedIn	link
80	VILABS	Social media post	VITALISE Summer School 2023	Facebook	link
81	VILABS	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Facebook	link
82	ENoLL	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	LinkedIn	link
83	ENoLL	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	LinkedIn	link
84	INTRAS	Social media post	Transnational Access Program	LinkedIn	link
85	INTRAS	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	LinkedIn	link
86	INTRAS	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	LinkedIn	link
87	INTRAS	Social media post	VITALISE recognition as a prime example of Best Practice in integrating Social Sciences and Humanities (#SSH)	LinkedIn	link
88	ENoLL	Social media post	VITALISE recognition as a prime example of Best Practice in integrating Social Sciences and Humanities (#SSH)	LinkedIn	link
89	SOCIAL IT (SIT)	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Twitter	link
90	ENoLL	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Twitter	link

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91	ENoLL	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Twitter	link
92	VILABS	Social media post	Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium	Twitter	link
93	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion 3rd open call	LinkedIn	link
94	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion 3rd open call	Twitter	link
95	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion newsletter	Twitter	link
96	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion VITALISE Master	LinkedIn	link
97	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation boot camp	LinkedIn	link
98	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation Vitalise Master	LinkedIn	link
99	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation boot camp	Instagram	link
100	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation boot camp	LinkedIn	link
101	INTRAS	Social media post	Pilot activity	Twitter	link
102	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion VITALISE Master	LinkedIn	link
103	INTRAS	Newsletter	Dissemination of VITALISE working group in SIVI Cluster Newsletter	Cluster SIVI_Boletín	link
104	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion boot camp	Twitter	link
105	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation boot camp	Instagram	link
106	INTRAS	News-item	Boot camp	Website	link
107	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion 3rd open call	Twitter	link
108	INTRAS	Social media post	Co-creation session	Twitter	link
109	INTRAS	Social media post	Promotion 2nd open call	Twitter	link
110	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation Vitalise Master	Twitter	link
111	INTRAS	Social media post	Participation Vitalise Master	LinkedIn	link
112	INTRAS	Social media post	Co-creation session	Twitter	link
113	INTRAS	Social media post	Co-creation session	Twitter	link
114	AUTH	Social Media Post	Info Day	Facebook	link
115	AUTH	Social Media Post	Open Call	Facebook	link

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116	AUTH	Social Media Post	MuseumDay/ co-creation session	Facebook	link
117	AUTH	Social Media Post & Newsletter	About Vitalise	Facebook & AUTH's Medical School Newsletter	link
118	AUTH	Social Media Post	VITALISE Project	Facebook	link
119	AUTH	Social Media Post	Xmas	Facebook	link
120	AUTH	Social Media Post	Icri 2022 side event!	Facebook	link
121	AUTH	Social Media Post	OpenCall	Facebook	link
124	AUTH	Social Media Post	OpenCall	Facebook	link
125	AUTH	Social Media Post	OpenCall	Facebook	link
126	AUTH	Social Media Post	METROXRINE IEEE Conference	Facebook	link
127	AUTH	Social Media Post	Transnational Access	Facebook	link
128	AUTH	Social Media Post	Info Day	Facebook	link
129	AUTH	Social Media Post	Open Call	Facebook	link
130	AUTH	Social Media Post	Happy Museum Day	Facebook	Link
131	AUTH	Social Media Post	Presentation	Facebook	Link
132	AUTH	Social Media Post	Summer School 2023	Facebook	Link
133	AUTH	Social Media Post	HTWG Konstanz : Medical Summer School	Facebook	Link
134	AUTH	Social Media Post	VITALISE Project webinar series!	Facebook	Link
135	AUTH	Social Media Post	LicaLab Visit	Facebook	Link

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136	AUTH	Social Media Post	Harmonization Body Meeting	Facebook	Link
137	AUTH	Social Media Post	OLLD2023	Facebook	Link
138	AUTH	Social Media Post	Building Bridges: Transdisciplinary Communication and Networking Strategies	Facebook	Link
139	AUTH	Social Media Post	1st Hellenic Living Lab Summit	Facebook	Link
140	AUTH	Social Media Post	Summer School 2023	Facebook	Link
141	AUTH	Social Media Post	Accelup Meeting	Facebook	Link
142	AUTH	Social Media Post	Call for External Evaluators	Facebook	Link
143	AUTH	Social Media Post	Plenary meeting	Facebook	Link
144	AUTH	Social Media Post	Plenary meeting	Facebook	Link
145	AUTH	Social Media Post	Open Call	Facebook	Link
146	AUTH	Social Media Post	INTEGER project meeting	Facebook	Link
147	AUTH	Social Media Post	Summer School 2023	Facebook	Link
148	AUTH	Social Media Post	Summer School 2023	Facebook	Link
149	AUTH	Social Media Post	VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp	Facebook	Link
150	AUTH	Social Media Post	Virtual Access	Facebook	Link
151	AUTH	Social Media Post	OLLD 2023	Facebook	Link
152	AUTH	Blogpost	VITALISE Project Summer School 2023 & Commercialization Bootcamp	Website	Link

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153	AUTH	Blogpost	VITALISE Project webinar series!	Website	Link
154	AUTH	Blogpost	Collaborating for Better Healthcare: University of Vlore Researchers Visit the Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation	Website	Link
155	AUTH	Blogpost	Happy Museum Day!	Website	Link
156	AUTH	Blogpost	ThessAHALL at the OLLD23!	Website	Link
157	AUTH	Blogpost	HTWG Konstanz: Medical Summer School	Website	Link
158	AUTH	Blogpost	Navigating Multitasking Realities in the Academic Digital Landscape	Website	Link
159	AUTH	Blogpost	Unveiling "ASSURE": Pioneering Dysphagia Screening with Cutting-Edge Technology	Website	Link
160	AUTH	Social Media Post	Breaking Barriers, Shaping Tomorrow	Facebook	Link
161	AUTH	Social Media Post	Pitch Clinic Event	Facebook	Link
162	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Call for TA 17/10/2022	Facebook	Link
163	TREBAG	Social Media Post	"2e Open Call VITALISE-project" 19/10/20202	Facebook	Link
164	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Periodic report of VITALISE 26/01/2023	Facebook	Link
165	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Partner meeting in Vienna 6/03/2023	Facebook	Link
166	TREBAG	Social Media Post	3rd Open Call VITALISE project 20/03/2023	Facebook	Link
167	TREBAG	Social Media Post	3rd Open Call VITALISE project /extended deadline 05/05/2023	Facebook	Link
168	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE Summer School 16/06/2023	Facebook	Link
169	TREBAG	Social Media Post	News about our JRA 19/07/2023	Facebook	Link
169	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Visiting professor TA VITALISE 19/07/2023	Facebook	Link
170	TREBAG	Social Media Post	News about our JRA 16/08/2023	Facebook	Link

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171	TREBAG	Social Media Post	TA VITALISE 08/09/223	Facebook	Link
172	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE on a sport congress in Gijon 24/09/2023	Facebook	Link
173	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Webinars in VITALISE 15/10/2023	Facebook	Link
174	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Blog published on our TA 25/10/2023	Facebook	Link
175	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Receiving an award with our presentation on VITALISE in Gijon 27/10/2023	Facebook	Link
176	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Vitalise on EUSportslab conference 10/12/2023	Facebook	Link
177	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Call for participation on VITALISE Symposium 17/01/2024	Facebook	Link
178	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE Day I – call 22/01/2024	Facebook	Link
179	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE Day I – report 30/01/2024	Facebook	Link
180	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE Pitch Clinic-call 07/02	Facebook	Link
181	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Participation at VITALISE Symposium 23/02/2024	Facebook	Link
182	TREBAG	Social Media Post	VITALISE Newsletter5 05/03/2024	Facebook	Link
183	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Call for Virtual Access 14/03/2024	Facebook	Link
184	TREBAG	Social Media Post	Participation at the Lille Ageing Fit Conference 21/03/2024	Facebook	Link
	TREBAG	Social media post (Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab)	Blog on VITALISE JRA	Facebook	Link
	TREBAG	Social media post (Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab)	Vitalise Symposium	Facebook	Link
	TREBAG	Social media post (Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab)	Vitalise Day I – call 22/01/2024	Facebook	Link

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TREBAG	Social media post (Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab)	Vitalise Pitch Clinic-call 07/02	Facebook	Link
TREBAG	Social media post (Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab)	Participation at the Lille Ageing Fit Conference 21/03/2024	Facebook	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	VA data base invitation 13/03/2024	Linkedin	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	2nd Open Call post 2023 March	Linkedin	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	TA access 2023 march	Linkedin	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	Infoday 2022 October	Linkedin	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	First call 2022 April	Linkedin	Link
TREBAG	Linkedin post	2022 February Open call for Evaluator	Linkedin	Link